

innochain

#1 | INNOCHAIN NETWORK JOURNAL

Innochain Network Journal #1

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itke - Institute of Building Structures and
Structural Design

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FIG. © ICD/ ITKE

Introduction

The Innochain Network Journal #1 presents the network events and training activities, that took place in the first 6 months of the InnoChain ETN network.

Innochain is a shared research training environment between 6 European academic environments and 14 industrial partners. The network examines how advances in digital design tools challenge building culture enabling sustainable, informed and materially smart design solutions. The network aims to train a new generation of interdisciplinary researchers with a strong industry focus that can effect real changes in the way we think, design and build our physical environment.

The Innochain training plan coordinates shared courses and evaluation events across the six institutions as a core platform for learning, exchange and collaboration. In the first six months the training programme has focussed on establishing a sense of community between the ESRs, enabling core theoretical and technical skills and creating a platform for the three scientific work packages. This was done through the Start Up seminar, the running of several scientific training courses and the workshop-seminar series 1.

The Innochain Journal #1 describes these events. The journal emphasises the workshop-seminars. The workshop-seminars are dual training events combining a hands-on workshop in which particular methods and tools are shared with a contextualising seminar with expert presentations. The workshop-seminars link to the 3 scientific work packages, Communicating Design (WP3), Simulation for Design (WP4) and Materialising Design (WP5), and hold a particular industry focus. The workshop-seminars were run respectively by CITA, ITKE and BSA.

The workshops series 1.0 examined the overarching topic: advanced timber construction. Undertaken in reverse order Workshop-Seminar 1.3 Materialising Design allowed ESRs to explore the planning,

steering and undertaking of robotic fabrication of timber elements, Workshop-Seminar 1.2 Simulation for Design examined design integrated simulation and Workshop-Seminar 1.1 Communicating Design asked ESRs investigated the differences that advanced timber construction can make in architecture.

Each workshop had its own aims, methods and connection to other events, such as the SimAUD conference which ESR were able to join as part of the Theories of Computation course (BSA).

The following chapters provide summaries of the events with examples of results and contributions from the ESRs. The journal foregrounds the wide array of training results: from build research prototypes to scientific essays.

We are very happy with the achieved breadth and quality of the first six months of Innochain training and hope to continue this in the future.

We thank all contributors of this journal and especially the editorial team from ITKE.

For the Supervisory Board of Innochain,
Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen and Martin Tamke

Editorial

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EDITORIAL

Welcome to this issue of the Innochain Network Journal, assembled and edited by ITKE. Following the Start-Up Seminar in March there have been six collaborative research and training events held by five of the Academic Partners, generating significant scientific output. It is our pleasure to be able to present some of those results within these pages.

The aim of the network, from the beginning, has been to examine “how advances in digital design tools challenge building culture enabling sustainable, informed and materially smart design solutions” (quote from Innochain Network summary). We believe that the work within this journal demonstrates that aim throughout.

We can be in no doubt that the continuing rise of digital technology and the increasing power of computation is having a visible impact on the built world. We are living in an age of apps, algorithms, uninhibited communication and ever-more-open digital fabrication machines, thus it is only right that the inherent future possibilities of these digital technologies are applied to the physical world we occupy. That is where the lines of inquiry within the Innochain Network begin.

Workshop-Seminars and Scientific Courses have provided lectures in current thinking, tuition in current techniques and space in which to consider these future possibilities. A common theme throughout the work has been on the embedment of knowledge from multiple parties into tools and process, enabling tighter integration of communicating, simulating and materialising design. Specific examples of this are touched upon in the reports from the Workshop-Seminars and further considered in the written papers from scientific courses. Dimitrie (D. Stefanescu, ESR05) postulates the possibility of mass creativity and the importance of knowledgeable feedback within this system whilst Giulio (G.Brugnaro, ESR10) considers the integration of craftsmanship in digital fabrication and the collaboration between the two different workers, human and robot. Zeynep (Z.Aksöz, ESR04) outlines the design potential of two collaborating minds, those

of human and artificial intelligence and Vasily (V.Sitnikov, ESR09) considers the pervasive influence of computational optimisation as it is further embedded into design process.

Another common theme found in this initial work is the consideration of specialised material design. Engineering and Architecture, aligned with the framework of Industry 4.0, are in a position to harness the power of computation to return to a more sensitive and efficient use of natural materials (lost in a world of mass standardisation) and to further utilise the un-obtained potentials of modern differentiable synthetic materials. This thread of research is the one most actively pursued in our work at itke, where we are investigating new methods of practical application for custom material designs/assemblies. Our work covers the development of new sustainable technical materials, the structural possibilities of customisable materials and the use of designed materials to integrate specific requirements, such as movement, into single components. The consideration of material properties in design features as a core part of the research work by the Innochain ESR's within our group and additionally this topic is presented in Tom's paper (T.Svilans, ESR02) on material communication where he considers the impact of computation on design process alongside the integration of material properties into the design of timber structures.

Whilst not directly covered within this journal it is worth highlighting the material contribution of the network so far. Two beta releases of the Speckle software tool by Dimitrie (D. Stefanescu, ESR05) are now available for public use, several research papers have been presented internationally and James (J.Solly, ESR08) worked on the design, fabrication and installation team for the Elytra Filament Pavilion in London. Further information on these can be found on the Innochain website.

There are many within the architecture and construction industry who are wary of the impact of computation on their field, with concerns ranging from design authorship to the ability of humans to accurately understand hyper-complex creations. It is clear from these concerns that the impact of computation is already here. Rather than calling for halt we propose considered research and we are therefore happy to be able to assemble this initial output from 15 motivated researchers working on aligned and highly collaborative projects. We are excited to see what further development the following years will bring.

The Editors,
Professor J. Knippers, J. Solly and E. Slabbinck

FIG. Flectofold - Bioinspired Kinetic Shading Device (by ITKE/ITF/IBB Stuttgart, PBG Tübingen, supported by DFG)

1.0 Workshop-Seminars

INTRODUCTION

The workshop-seminars are the core research instrument of the network scientific training provision. Each Innochain workshop-seminar is a dual-training event that includes both expert presentations and a hands-on workshop in which particular methods and tools are shared and collaboratively developed.

The first three workshop-seminars have now taken place, one for each of the three scientific work packages: Communicating Design, Simulating Design and Materialising Design. The workshop-seminar relevant to each ESR's individual research project was compulsory for them to attend, with the other workshop-seminars available as optional courses.

Workshop 1.1: Communicating Design was held at CITA and focussed on the topic of "Future Wood". A day-long expert seminar was followed by the development of three group research projects that are summarised in the following pages.

Workshop 1.2: Simulating Design was held at itke and introduced the ESRs to generalised simulation software tools through taught examples and expert demonstrations. This was followed by a hackathon type session in which individual projects were developed. Summaries of these projects are presented in the following pages.

Workshop 1.3: Materialising Design was held at the Bartlett and revolved around a workshop-based fabrication challenge. The ESRs were introduced to robotic timber fabrication tools and then competed in groups to design and construct towers capable of supporting a set load at 2m height with the minimum material possible.

1.1 Communicating Design

FUTURE WOOD
CITA (COPENHAGEN)
22 - 24 JUNE 2016

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WORKSHOP - SEMINARS

Led by Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen and Martin Tamke with Jacob Riiber Nielsen

INTRODUCTION

In June 2017 CITA held the last of the three research workshop seminars: Design, Engineering and Fabrication of Timber Structures. The workshop-seminar takes point of the departure in the discussions and experiments of the two proceeding workshop seminars in the Innochain network, which explored material processing and simulation of wood. This seminar asks what the architectural - spatial, social or environmental - consequences of such structural and material studies are. The workshop-seminar had a two fold focus:

- To examine contemporary use, design and analysis of timber structures
- To investigate how material thinking can lead to new spatial concepts

The workshop-seminar was structured around a full day seminar with invited international speakers from research and practice and followed by a two-day workshop with ESRs.

FIG. LEFT PAGE Nine Bridges Country Club by Shigeru Ban

FIG. RIGHT PAGE Vennesla Library and Culture House by Helen & Hard // Oakwood Tower by PLP, Cambridge University

The seminar "Future Wood" introduced leading European practitioners presenting the state of the art of current timber construction and ranged from advanced timber projects from practice to speculative research enquiries. With presentations from Reinhard Kropf from Helen and Hardt (NO), Johannes Kuhnen from Design to Production (CH), Kevin Flanagan, PLP Architects (UK) and Søren Hell Hansen from CF Møller (DK) the field of advanced timber construction for the built environment was broadly presented, showcasing the complex interactions between design realisation and the complexity of construction timber structures. These presentations were held together with speculative and research focussed presentations from Martin Self from the Architectural Association (UK), Martin Tamke from CITA and Christopher Robeller from EPFL (CH). By bringing together applied research from practice with ground research from leading institutions across Europe a broad debate of the possibilities for working strategically with renewable materials was enabled. The following 2 day workshop explored how material thinking can lead to new spatial concepts and develops architectural propositions as a means of exploring these. It took point of departure in the unique ability of architecture to engage and reinterpret state of the art technologies in a speculative manner. The architectural techniques, such as drawing or the production of scaled physical models, is today

FIG. LEFT Hook park by AA Design and Make

FIG. RIGHT Blind, Deaf and Dumb by Richard Deacon

extended through generative design strategies, simulation and digital fabrication. These ideas were presented in an introductory lecture in which examples of futurisms informed by material systems were presented from across architectural history.

The aim of the workshop was to extend upon the experiments from workshop-seminar 1.3 (testing robotic milling for timber joints) and 1.2 (simulating anisotropic behaviour in timber). By introducing a set of generative tools, the workshop explores how a particular material strategy can be encoded and thus formalised and propagated within a design solution.

The workshop asked ESRs to reflect on:

- What are the spatial consequences of a particular material logic?
- What are the architectural traditions for these kinds of conceptual enquiries?
- What are the means by which such investigations can be undertaken?

WORKSHOP RESULTS

Workshop participants worked in three groups. Each group aimed to create synergy between the individual ESR research projects and the overall workshop theme.

FIG. Group picture of the participants at the workshop

Group 1 - Urban Intervention

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Tom Svilans
Paul Poinet
Kasper Ax

ESR NUMBER: ESR02, ESR06, ESR14
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Bluhmer Lehmann,
Buro Happold, designtoproduction, white
INSTITUTE: CITA

INTRODUCTION

This workshop seminar offered an opportunity for three ESRs to collaborate around the shared topic of engineered timber design and construction. The series of lectures at the beginning of the workshop offered a large variety of approaches and techniques in contemporary timber design, fabrication, and research. Each offered a distinct trajectory and realm of application at a distinct scale, in a way staking out the territory of cutting-edge timber architecture. The workshop thus was an opportunity to contextualize the individual ESRs within this territory and speculate about the broader implications of each research project. The first research project, ESR2, is focused around the integration of early-stage design, material performance, digital fabrication technologies, and current industrial processes in laminated timber construction. It addresses the design-to-production chain and questions how new technologies and digital techniques can improve, hybridize, or re-think current modes of laminated timber design and production. It is therefore positioned towards some of the more experimental topics in the workshop - the 3d scanning and robotic machining at Hooke Park as presented by Martin Self, Architectural Association, and the prototyping and

design-make strategies presented by Helen and Hard as presented by Reinhard Kropf. The second research project, ESR6, is focused on the design exploration of free-form timber elements using one or multiple master surfaces in order to drive the global design. Another aspect investigated the potential of linking different scales together, from the main structural elements to secondary timber beams that could be aggregated in different locations for achieving different enclosures and spatial/architectural qualities. The third research project, ESR10, deals with notions of assembly logistics and design for manufacture, wherein parameters that typically come at the very end of the design-to-production chain are considered and designed for well in advance, in tandem with other early-stage design issues. The collaboration during the workshop was an attempt to forge common links between all three ESR projects and evaluate the feasibility of developing digital workflows between each project, with the ultimate aim of arriving at a shared goal - a physical demonstrator that could become a testing ground for all three projects. With this in mind, the workshop was approached as a design brief - a large-scale urban intervention, extrapolating the fledgling research explorations

almost ad absurdum to visualize what the much broader implications may be. As a result, the design project was fast and playful, choosing naive speculation over rigid experimentation.

PROCESS

Using the Grasshopper environment and different custom scripts (in Python or in C#), it has been possible to generate different design features, from two-dimensional and surface-based geometries

FIG. TOP Different hierarchies are used for different design iterations

FIG. BOTTOM Design iteration of a network of massive glulam beams as a proposed urban intervention

to complete three-dimensional typologies. Different hierarchies have also been introduced through the different networks of timber elements by using different sizings, types of cross sections, dimensions and branching strategies.

The workshop allowed the exploration of different design potentials, from integrated computational design workflows to more heterogeneous typologies. This investigation led to a general discussion about the global design and further construction of a demonstrator that would take into account different material specifications and fabrication processes.

The proposal was an urban intervention in the heart of Copenhagen: a network of massive glulam buildings and infrastructure which spanned from Amager to Christiania, occupying most of the Kløvermarken greenspace. The driving idea behind the proposal was the question of what an environment framed by massive free-form glulam construction would look like and how it could be inhabited. Taking precedent from existing large-scale glulam projects such as Pompidou Metz and the Omega Swatch building, it proposed a large structural network that would host services, infrastructure, and habitable spaces. This was a reconception of glulam members simply as structural components, imbuing them with programme and function beyond simply supporting structural loads. The glulam as a composite performing element - not simply a structural member - was taken to the large scale where it could be inhabited, interacted with, and used for services and utilities.

OBSERVATIONS

The different design iterations realized by the three ESRs led them to discuss the different aesthetic implications of the different undertaken design workflows and strategies, from heterogeneous aspects to more integrative aesthetics. Contrary to an integrative parametric workflow, a "heterogeneous" model can interrelate objects only through abstract hierarchical information (without linking parametrically the different objects themselves). In this case,

there exists no clear and defined aesthetic implication concerning the resulting architectural design project. This presents a decoupling of the abstract framework from its implementation, or component elements. The potential consequence of this method of working is a design model or network which allows for interruptions and unexpected exceptions to its base logic.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

This workshop served as a strong basis for the further development of a demonstrator made of free-formed timber elements by the three ESRs involved in the described design explorations. While it was a good opportunity to pull back and speculate about the broader architectural implications of the involved construction methods and design models, the opposite end of the scale - the world of fabrication, tolerance, and individual elements - was pushed to the background. To address this, a future model could work from the bottom up, thereby linking the micro- and meso- scales more tightly with the broader visionary implications, resulting in a more nuanced

FIG. Basis for further development of a demonstrator

proposal, while remaining just as ambitious.

Further work will be undertaken in order to refine and tune the design exploration by taking more into account material performance and fabrication constraints necessary for the completion of the mentioned demonstrator.

FIG. TOP Free form timber elements as demonstrator proposal

FIG. BOTTOM Design iteration of a network of massive glulam beams as a proposed urban intervention

Group 2 - Wind Harvesting

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Angelos Chronis
Evy L. M. Slabbinck

ESR NUMBER: ESR03, ESR01
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG, FOSTER + PARTNERS,
MCNEEL
INSTITUTE: IAAC, ITKE

INTRODUCTION

The goal of the workshop is to reflect on the students' PhD topic and place this in a global and futuristic perspective. The reflection and synergy between the students enables them to think beyond the bubble they are working in every day.

This project creates synergy between two simulation-focused topics, on the one hand Angelos Chronis - working with 'Integrating building physics for Performance Control' and CFD simulations- on the other hand Evy L. M. Slabbinck - working on 'Integrating Isogeometric Analysis'. The collaboration between both projects is not as straightforward, as the reflection into a future perspective of the topics in a single matter is already a challenge.

The first research topic focuses on the integration of performance feedback in the design process. The design complexity that has been brought about in architecture by the continuous development of computational design processes, digital fabrication and advanced materiality are already demanding a more integrated approach to performance feedback and simulation. Computational Fluid

Dynamics (CFD) simulations, which have numerous applications in building physics problems, such as natural and mechanical ventilation, pedestrian comfort, structural analysis etc. are still an unexplored area in computational design. In the context of the workshop, this project envisions a design process, where CFD simulations are integrated in computational design.

The second research topic deals with the integration of a new topic in architecture and engineering and how this could be applied for future advantages in the industry. Current research conducted shows the use of IGA granted for large deformations and contact problems. Lightweight structures, bending-active tensile structures in particular, introduce a complexity on several levels that justify the use of IGA. The use of IGA in the future and the relevance of the subject is the actual topic of the research. The proposition of bending-active tensile structures as an example structure for a simple integration of design, simulation and analysis in the future shows the potential of the new analysis method.

PROCESS

Software utilised: Grasshopper [1], Rhinoceros [2], Sketchup [3] and CFD [4].

Major cities are evolving on a daily basis, and growing in width and height. More skyscrapers are built and enabling problems regarding exhausts, wind, green, etc. The collaboration between wind analysis and bending-active tensile structures wants to respond to this.

Built bending-active tensile structures remain on a pavilion-scale and are built in a research environment. This is partly due to the complexity of the reciprocity of the form-active structure that makes the simulation, fabrication and construction difficult. These lightweight structures have a lot of advantages and potentials but stay within temporary small-scale milieu.

The project acts on an urban scale and searches for the advantage of using large-scale bending-active tensile structures in relation to wind flows. Renewable energy, harvesting wind, CO₂ ventilating are current topics that will only become more important in the future and could be a potential integration of both topics.

FIG. Geometry wind-harvesting funnel shape bending-active tensile structure

On the one hand a wind analysis is conducted of Manhattan as an example city and on the other hand a lightweight geometry was designed to be able to work as a funnel to fit between high-rise buildings (Figure 01 and 02). The CFD analysis of Manhattan shows the wind velocity and direction through the streets and along the buildings (Figure 03), these streamlines can be converted to vectors and exported to a 3D file of Manhattan. The direction of the vectors are directly mapped with the funnel shaped bending-active tensile structures.

FIG. TOP Concept geometry

FIG. BOTTOM Streamlines as a result of CFD simulation

RESULTS

The results aim to demonstrate the potential of a direct integration of CFD simulations in a computational design process. As a proof of concept a fast CFD simulation that has been previously developed by Chronis [4] was integrated in the parametric design of the bending-active tensile structures. The use and relevance of bending-active tensile structures is increased to an urban scale and the close collaboration between structure, simulation and design is validated, which enables the use of IGA (Figure 04 and 05).

The overall process shows how CFD simulations could be coupled with the IGA in a generative design process that drives the form of the bending-active tensile wind catchers to optimize the generation of wind and to improve the air quality of the city. The harvesting of the wind could be done with the EWICON (Electrostatic Wind Energy Converter) technology, which is a bladeless windmill. The advantage of this system is that it is a lightweight technology that makes no noise [5]. Then, through an optimization process with the integration of CFD the form of the structure could be also optimised to take advantage of the Venturi effect and cool down the temperature of the summer winds.

FIG. Integration of the system in a futuristic city

CONCLUSION

Overall, the Future Wood workshop was a good opportunity to contextualize both projects within futuristic, yet very tangible scenarios of architectural projects. The workshop's process revealed interesting issues, both in terms of the collaboration between the ESRs, such as file and data exchange and input/output strategies for the design, as well as in terms of the potential of an integrated innovative design process.

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- [5] EWICON by Mecanoo, www.21stcentech.com

FIG. Integration of the system in a futuristic city

Group 3 - Future of Design Thinking

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Zeynep Aksoz
Dimitrie A. Stefanescu

ESR NUMBER: ESR04, ESR05
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG, HENN GmbH,
STR.UCTURE
INSTITUTE: IOA, BSA

INTRODUCTION

The Future Wood seminar's general focus was on combination of different research topics of the Innochain ESRs and the creation of an "utopian vision" through application of the developed strategies during the workshop. The seminar started with an intense series of presentations that display different approaches on constructing with wood, from small to large scale examples, from constructive logics to artistic intentions. The following days it was required to focus on personal topics in a team environment and develop an approach through synergies between the aims of the researchers in the team.

This project represents the collaboration between the ESRs Zeynep Aksöz (IoA) and Dimitrie Stefanescu (BSA). Zeynep Aksöz's topic is Multiple Criteria Optimization in Early Design Phase. Her main interest lays in emergent design processes through human-machine collaboration, where both parts are seen as stakeholders within a non-hierarchical system. She focuses on artificial intelligence and the interface between human intuition and computer logic, where influence of both parts achieves the design goal.

Dimitrie Stefanescu is researching how complex simulation-based design can be collated and communicated externally – technical stakeholders - and internally – non-technical stakeholders. His main focus is on developing & technically enabling a methodological approach through which digital parametric models can be used as conduits for a transparent and engaging process of collaborative problem definition and value creation in the production of the built environment.

Both research topics focus on a kind of collaborative working, where multiple stakeholders whether human or machine are involved in decision making during the design process. Through this collaboration the design starts to become an emergent result of interacting dynamics between the decisions of the stakeholders.

Therefore, the project's main interest was to discuss the future of design thinking where multiple stakeholders are involved in design in real-time in the same computational environment. Investigating such an approach in an intense workshop would provide an overview on the benefits and limitations of the aims of both researchers.

PROCESS

Even though the workshop required to select a certain utopian spatial setting, it was decided not to concentrate on a physical environment since both ESRs topics were not relying on the physical nor geometrical design background rather theoretical methodologies on conducting or understanding design. Instead of concentrating on a physical result three separate systems of stakeholders were selected to simulate the goals of both ESRs. One human designer and two algorithmic settings were selected to investigate the interaction between these three intelligent systems that dynamically react on each other's behavior. Consequently, the final design would be a result of two machine based dynamic systems and a human collaborator.

The project was tested in the Grasshopper environment in Rhino using Speckle as a data communication platform. Speckle is a plugin for Grasshopper (in development by Dimitrie Stefanescu) where the certain outputs of a Grasshopper Code can be collated and communicated dynamically to other stakeholders. It allows for the interweaving of parametric logic in a dynamic way, unrestricted

FIG. Initial test of the algorithm merger: blue lines represent the branching algorithm, green lines the agent trails

to one software instance or one author, essentially fostering the emergence of various workflows. By storing the transmitted data against a set of defined keys, it enables a comprehensive exploration of the solution space (as defined by input criteria and performance measures).

In the first day of the workshop several methods involving Genetic Algorithms using Octopus Explicit components, branching systems on dynamically changing surfaces, agent based systems dynamically reacting on the branching algorithms were tested and evaluated regarding the compatibility on speckle environment, the computation speed on remote and overall computation time. The tests with the Genetic Algorithms were basing on the data that is building upon a real time received data from another computer, in this case the data was a design solution. Where the first computer keeps sending information second computer generates derivatives of the design solution relying on the sent information and evaluates these within the GA. However, these tests ended up in long calculation times that eventually crush the program.

FIG. Testing the algorithm's flexibility: instead of generic spherical surface, a pavilion-like shape is used

As a result, Genetic Algorithms which rely on long iterative computation processes were decided to be avoided during this workshop due to time limitations compared to the long decision making process using GAs. However, in the future it was decided to test the process with these kinds of applications as well.

Consequently, for the further tests a set up was selected that needs less calculation time. In the final set up 3 systems were observed. Each system was building on top of the previous system. In this case the first system was a collection of surfaces created in 3d modelling platform Rhinoceros. This collection was generating an enclosed space basing on double layered doubly curved surfaces. The secondary system was taking these collection of surfaces as a base and generating a branching structure on top of each singular surface.

The branching algorithm was searching iteratively closest points to grow to within a constrained angle and distance. This way in each iteration new branches were generated until the entire surface was filled with branches, no space else was left for the growth. However, this algorithm was reacting in real-time to certain changes in the previous surface collection. If the user was increasing the surface area by modifying the geometry the growth could continue until the new area was covered. At the end of the manual modelling and branching processes a double layered branching structure was generated. The third system was building upon the secondary structure and generating an agent-based weaving system that connects upper and lower layer between each other.

This process was divided between two computers. In the first computer the user was creating the surfaces and the branching algorithm was responding in real-time to user's decisions. The surfaces and the branches were transmitted (via Speckle) to the second computer where the agent-based simulation was reacting on the previous two processes also in real-time. The interesting part in this experiment was while the branching algorithm was running

on one computer the branching information was sent dynamically to the other computer by Speckle, where the agent code was running. The agent-based system was reacting to the growth of the branches in real-time, and it was updating itself with the new growth.

CONCLUSIONS

At the end of the workshop several tests showed that an online data communication platform (i.e., Speckle) can help avoid top-down approaches in the design process. The stakeholders can work on different parts of a project by influencing and reacting on each other's decisions in real-time only by sharing the necessary information with the other stakeholders. The updates on the code can be received in real-time or be frozen to a certain variation in order to work separately. On the one hand this collaborative working method can avoid long file exchange processes. Furthermore, it allows for the design to become a symbiotic process between the various actors involved – human or algorithms.

FIG. Final test branching algorithm on multiple surfaces combined with weaving agents reaching on branching systems in real time

Communicating Design: Conclusions

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

SEMINAR CONCLUSIONS

Through the participation of the ESRs as well as a open public audience a broad discussion about the future of timber architecture was enabled which led to the success of the seminar. Their presentations highlighted the many levels, which need to be addressed in order to drive innovation in architecture - from a technological-material to political-sustainable level. Especially Reinhard Kropf's (Helen and Hardt, NO) presentation synthesised the many concerns in working with timber, from questions of sustainable materials, fabrication and the problems of acoustics. This very applied research was interestingly contrasted with the research presented by Martin Self (Architectural Association, UK) and Martin Tamke (CITA, DK) who discussed speculative approaches to forest management (scanning timber stock using 3D scanning or photogrammetry), joinery (using found timber) and analysis (working with design integrated simulation). A second theme to the discussion was the role of architecture as a projective art. Especially the presentation of Kevin Flanagan from PLP architects and his presentation of their timber high rise project, London's first wooden skyscraper and a 300-metre-tall addition to the Barbican housing estate.

WORKSHOP

The two-day workshop made for a very compressed timeframe. The task to synthesise and collaborate between individual research projects was not equally simple for all participants and groups. The ESRs took this challenge well and used the workshop to test the robustness of the techniques they developed and explore new areas for applications in an unconstrained way.

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

Evy Slabbinck (ITKE)

Tom Svilans (CITA)

Angelos Chronis (IAAC)

Zeynep Aksoz (IOA)

Dimitrie A. Stefanescu (BSA)

Paul Poinet (CITA)

Kaspar Ax (CITA)

1.2 Simulating Design

GENERAL PURPOSE SOLVER FOR PROJECT-SPECIFIC SIMULATION
ITKE (STUTT GART)
30 MAY - 02 JUNE 2016

Led by Daniel Piker (Foster+Partners/McNeel), Harri Lewis (mule) and Long Nguyen (ICD, University of Stuttgart) with James Solly (ITKE, University of Stuttgart)

INTRODUCTION

This workshop-seminar, held in May/June 2016 by ITKE, featured as part of the “Simulating Design” work package of the Innochain Network. The use of relevant simulation within the process of construction is one of the primary considerations of the Innochain research projects. With the majority of the ESR’s planning to use computational simulation within their research it was considered relevant to provide a workshop environment in which they could experiment with a generalised and customisable constraint-based simulation tool.

KANGAROO PHYSICS

Kangaroo is a plugin for the Grasshopper visual programming environment that has been developed by Daniel Piker since 2010. It simulates physical behaviour at interactive speed using dynamic relaxation techniques.

FIG. LEFT PAGE V&A Elytra Filament Pavilion by ICD/ ITKE, ©NAARO

FIG. RIGHT PAGE Innochain participants attending the workshop

The current version, Kangaroo2, operates in a manner inspired by position-based dynamics. The tool enables the combination of multiple constraints or “Goals” in order to assemble unique solutions for generalised problems. Additionally, and importantly for the Innochain 1.2 Workshop, the solver can also be accessed through an API, such that individual users may code their own problem-specific Goals in addition to those that ship with the tool.

WORKSHOP

The workshop was led by the creator of Kangaroo Physics, Daniel Piker with support from other experts (see top). At the beginning of the 4-day workshop, Daniel introduced the Kangaroo Physics software and the built-in functionality that is available to the general user. Following this he taught the group how to create their own customised components and at this stage the active development began, to continue for the rest of the week.

With a number of projects investigating increased intelligence in the use of anisotropic materials for construction, the workshop had a specific focus on the development of possible simulation strategies for these using Kangaroo Physics. This included a presentation from Research Associate Dylan Wood (ICD), who demonstrated some of his work on simulating the humidity-activated bending behaviour of timber laminates and a presentation from Professor Jan Knippers (ITKE) on the institute’s current research.

In addition to the creation of custom goals, during the middle of the workshop the group investigated the ability to control the Kangaroo2 solver itself through a scripted interface, enabling direct control of the physical system during the solution.

This control has the potential to enable variations in model topology and goal behaviour during the solution, further broadening the application of the solver.

WORKSHOP RESULTS

For the end of the workshop, all participants presented the projects they had developed during the week to the group and a discussion was held regarding possible further development opportunities.

Summaries of the individual projects are contained in the following pages.

Project 1 - Volumetric Discretization for Anisotropic Material Simulation

Tom Svilans

ESR NUMBER: ESR02

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Blumer Lehmann, WHITE

INSTITUTE: CITA

INTRODUCTION

The project was an exploration of dynamic relaxation tools (Kangaroo / Piker) and they could be applied to simulate anisotropic behaviour in beam elements. The project dealt with the volumetric discretization of models and the translation of these discrete elements into relaxation constraints and goals. It also looked at how these tools could simulate the effects of changing the anisotropic directions within the same model volume.

PERSONAL PROJECT

The project began by questioning how a volume composed of multiple anisotropic sub-volumes – arranged in different orientations – would behave under simple loads and forces. This was in line with a larger research question that addresses timber lamination and the strategic fibre orientation within such laminations. Instead of using established FEA tools, the project used a dynamic relaxation solver (Kangaroo) to better understand the process of setting up and simulating anisotropic effects.

Simple study cases were set up, each a simple beam or other prismatic volume with one or more anisotropic sub-volumes. These

were simply modelled in Rhinoceros 3D and meshed. A custom script was used to export the meshes to a format usable by TetGen, a tetrahedral mesh generator and 3D Delaunay triangulator (<http://wias-berlin.de/software/tetgen/>). The results of the discretization were re-imported into Rhino using custom scripts. The edges of the resultant tetrahedra were converted to line springs with varying stiffnesses, depending on their length and orientation. The dominant 'grain' direction for each volume affected the stiffness of each edge: those edges more in-line with the grain direction were stiffer than those who were perpendicular to it. These goals were then input into the solver with some additional anchor and force goals to simulate fixing points and loads. The resultant difference in length of each edge was mapped to a colour gradient to identify areas of tension and areas of compression.

The resulting deformations seemed to respond to different anisotropic orientations as expected, though cross-checking with an established FEA package would have helped gauge the success of the experiment. Overall, the project helped to understand the process of volume discretization and the implementation of anisotropic constraints in the Rhino + Kangaroo environment. Data interchange between Rhino, Kangaroo, and TetGen was fleshed out and custom Kangaroo goals were implemented as part of the process.

CONCLUSION

The relevance of this project to the overall PhD was significant in the sense that it opened up a method to create preliminary simulations of complex laminated assemblies. The strategic orientation of wood fibre in a laminated assembly needs to be simulated and validated, therefore the introduction of these tools is paramount to beginning work in that direction. The ultimate aim is to develop a robust workflow which implements the simulation of anisotropic timber elements to iteratively optimize and inform design models and the production of physical prototypes.

Project 2 - Façade Panelisation through Geometry Packing

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Zeynep Aksöz

ESR NUMBER: ESR04
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG, STR.UCTURE
INSTITUTE: IOA

FIG. Packing algorithm running

In the Workshop Simulating Anisotropic Material in Stuttgart the main focus was on developing simulation tools with Kangaroo 2 library and plug in. I took this opportunity to develop a tool for the case study I am working on with my industrial partners. The case study was covering a façade optimization of a triangulated surface and the method I wanted to test was creating triangulated larger modules and packing these on a surface in order to keep the variation on the façade but also reduce the complexity in fabrication.

Firstly, I have started with a circle packing on surface method, and created a tool that can interact with the changes in the geometry. The concentration of the circles can follow an attractor point interactively. Also the change of the size of the base or the radius of the packed circles can trigger the algorithm to produce more circles interactively. (fig. 1 to 6)

This experiment was displaying the general idea of packing the same module on the surface but the aim was to do this with custom generated polygonal surfaces, so the user can test different modular options. Therefore, I have developed a tool, using Kangaroo 2 library. The tool was basing on a basic circle packing algorithm but rather than packing equally sized circles on a surface it is packing any type of closed polyline geometry on a surface by using collision detection. (fig.7) However the tool is not working perfectly due to the spread that is happening through collision of two polylines.

FIG. Packing custom polygons on a surface

Project 3 - Multi-Scale Volumetric Material Simulation

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Paul Poinet

ESR NUMBER: ESR06

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold,
designtoproduction

INSTITUTE: CITA

FIG. LEFT PAGE Exploded diagram representing the updated position of all tetrahedrons

FIG. RIGHT PAGE Discretization of a complex timber member using TetGen and Kangaroo 2

INTRODUCTION

During this workshop, I investigated the three-dimensional discretization of glue-laminated timber beams in order to run further dynamic relaxations (using Kangaroo2) that could simulate the material behaviour of free-form and complex timber elements.

PERSONAL PROJECT

In order to discretize a volume into a series of tetrahedrons, I used the TetGen library (<http://wias-berlin.de/software/tetgen/>). The latter allowed me to input any sort of triangulated closed mesh whose edges and vertices could serve as anchor points for further three-dimensional subdivision. This particular aspect enabled me to keep track of data hierarchy between different types of resolution. For example, the fiber orientation along the beam (or along the V-Direction) was preserved after three-dimensional subdivision.

During simulation, the constraints placed in the solver were simple Unary Forces which could be constantly modified and replaced by the user in order to predict the bending-active behavior of the three-dimensional timber beam under specific loads.

CONCLUSION

The workshop enabled me to conduct specific research on the topic of Multi-Scalar Modelling, where I investigated the potential of modelling and transferring geometrical information across different resolutions, from an initial coarse mesh to finer resolution - through three dimensional subdivision and dynamic relaxation.

Project 4 - Form-Finding with Anisotropic Constraints

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Christoph Hermann

ESR NUMBER: ESR07

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Cloud 9, Blumer Lehmann

INSTITUTE: IOA

I have used this workshop to find alternative methods to FEM analysis to simulate anisotropy as means of form-finding using dynamic mesh relaxation tool Kangaroo2. While this method is not necessarily accurate (although it could be, dependent on input data) it is extremely fast and allows as high degree of interaction. During the workshop I built a series of tools relevant for my research.

BENDING-ACTIVE

A simple Grasshopper definition simulating a bent circular rod within an elastic membrane. In contrast to many active bending simulations rod and textile are not connected allow for a multitude of volumetric configurations on a single model. The concept is inspired by the BMW concept car Gina.

FIG. Simulating Design workshop custom Kangaroo2 goal ForceDependentEllipse-Packing

ELLIPSE PACKING

Using a series of scripted custom goals resulted in a Kangaroo2 definition allowing orientated and scale depended ellipse packing based on an arbitrary vector field. This concept will be further refined using custom loops to integrate with structural data from Karamba3d.

ANISOTROPIC BENDING

Various studies using my custom script for evenly placed streamline placement have been carried out to control mesh properties with additional custom goals in kangaroo2. This has been used to control material behaviour and simulate certain anisotropic behaviours. The concept will now be further investigated.

FIG. TOP Digitally simulating anisotropic behaviour using a streamline articulation

FIG. BOTTOM Digitally simulating anisotropic behaviour using a vector field

Project 5 - Virtual Prototyping of FRP Fabrication Strategies

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

James Solly

ESR NUMBER: ESR08
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold,
Foster + Partners
INSTITUTE: ITKE

INTRODUCTION

The research topic I am pursuing is in Virtual Prototyping FRP, particularly focussing on the development of tools to improve the process of Coreless Filament Winding. In this fabrication method the resulting geometry is directly linked to the sequence of fabrication steps. During the Simulating Design workshop I further developed some potential simulation methods for the understanding of filament behaviour during the winding process.

PERSONAL PROJECT

My project aimed to create an iterative procedure for the placement of fibres within a 3d space, allowing newly added fibres to interact with those placed in previous steps. The first step to enable this involved the creation of a customised solver goal for Kangaroo2. This is built around a mathematical description of a filament as a polyline. The internal nodes are free to move along the filament but the length of the filament is maintained with a correctly-described material stiffness. In the diagram below, the starting geometry is arbitrary but the solved geometry is a direct result of the force actions on the fibre. The load application points may be considered as running on pulley

wheels so the resulting fibre geometry has an equal tension in all segments i.e. $T_a = T_b = T_c$.

This goal was successfully developed in a simple form during the workshop. Significant further development is planned for this goal but a good initial result was obtained.

The second step was to create a geometric framework that would perform the initial geometric intersection detection and define the input to the simulation. This part of the project was developed based on discussions with my colleague at the University of Stuttgart, Marshall Prado (ICD) regarding some of his earlier research. During the workshop, a strategy was developed to incorporate this geometric operation into a loop with the Kangaroo2 solver and custom goal described above.

FIG. TOP Polyline Pulley Goal Operation

FIG. BOTTOM Initial steps towards simulating a coreless-filament-wound component

Project 6: Simulation of Subtractive Fabrication Techniques

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

Giulio Brugnaro

ESR NUMBER: ESR10
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG, ROK
INSTITUTE: BSA

INTRODUCTION

The workshop focused on developing simulation strategies for cutting/carving/tearing techniques with mesh-based geometries through the live physics engine "Kangaroo 2" for Rhino/Grasshopper. These processes are particularly relevant to the ESR10 "Simulating Robotic Feedback", which aims to establish a simulation environment for subtractive fabrication techniques that could be constantly tuned and updated with real-time sensor data.

PERSONAL PROJECT

The main components of the simulation are the dynamic "cutter" tool and the mesh to cut. Beside fixing the naked vertices of the mesh with the "Anchor" goal, each edge is transformed into a spring with the "Length" goal in order to give some resistance to the material from immediately tearing apart as the cutter moves through. The cutter, which is movable, works as a repulsing agent, pushing away the nearby vertices of the mesh. If the repelling force is higher than a predefined threshold, the springs that are holding together the mesh break, the vertices get disjointed and fall apart far away from each other.

The main parameters used to tune the simulation are the geometry of the cutter, its force and influence range together with the resistance threshold of the material being cut. It has been possible to achieve this through a combination of ready-made goals and some custom ones written in C# during the workshop. While the simulation showed a promising representation of the tearing/breaking of meshes, a major challenge that hasn't been implemented yet would be to actually break apart topologically the mesh and define two, or more, new meshes generated out of the action of the cutting tool.

CONCLUSION

While Kangaroo2 might not be the preferred tool to simulate subtractive techniques where part of the material is completely removed rather than bent, deformed or dislocated, further developments of the simulation strategy developed during the workshop could bring significant benefits due to the robustness and high performances of the new solver, especially in the perspective of using the tool within a real-time fabrication process. Furthermore, the workshop has been a valuable conceptual exercise aimed to establish which are the components necessary to simulate subtractive fabrication techniques within a digital framework and how the interaction among these could be abstracted and modelled.

FIG. Ball breaking mesh (Left to right, top to bottom)

Simulating Design: Conclusions

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WORKSHOP-SEMINARS

CONCLUSIONS

The workshop was a focussed series of sessions providing both taught material and expert-supported project development. Within this specifically-arranged environment, most of the ESRs in attendance achieved interesting and relevant outcomes for their future use. The most progressed projects made significant use of programming in C#, a task that was not simple for all attendees, but even just using the standard set of tools some good progress was made.

The workshop differed from some others by providing several days purely aimed towards development, more akin to a Hackathon than a general seminar. By avoiding significant lecture-provided content the ESRs were able to spend much more time investigating their own interests within a collaborative group.

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

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Zeynep Aksoz (IOA)

Paul Poinet (CITA)

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James Solly (ITKE)

Vasily Sitnikov (KTH)

Giulio Brugnaro (BSA)

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Kaspar Ax (CITA)

1.3 Materialising Design

DESIGN FOR PRODUCTION WITH ROBOTICS
THROUGH CONSTRAINTS
BMADE, BSA (LONDON)
11 - 13 MAY 2016

Led by: Prof. Bob Sheil, Prof. Stephen Gage, Dr. Sean Hanna, Vicente Soler, Peter Scully (technical Director BMADE)

Technical Support: Inigo Dodd (NC Manager) Vincent Huyghe (BMADE Teaching Fellow)

OVERVIEW:

The workshop plan evolved around:

1. Real world production constraints
2. Exploitation of these constraints in delivering a design brief
3. Investigating the impact of the constraint and design approach to mitigate/exploit the constraint

The brief: To design and build a structure that will hold a 0.5-meter sphere filled with water at 2000mm from the floor level. The structure can only use 50 X 50mm Douglas Fir timber as a construction material. All cutting will be within a robot milling cell (KUKA KR60 HA with DKP 400 2-axis positioner) using a 15.87mm (5/8^{ths} of an inch) spindle mounted end mill. All joints will be dry assembled and held in place with a 16mm wooden dowel. Every connection, and in turn every part, must be unique. All assembly is to be by hand. Any software can

FIG. LEFT PAGE Close-up of one of the projects

FIG. RIGHT PAGE Action pictures of the construction process

be used for the creation of production information, however the final instruction to the robot milling cell will be via Grasshopper Plugin through Rhino, so experience of these will be useful. No previous experience of Robotic machining is necessary. The final and most important constraint was that the teams had 3 days to complete and reach a physical conclusion.

DAY 1: The work-package:

The brief was introduced to the 10 attending ESR's on the morning of the 11th May by Prof. Bob Sheil and Peter Scully. The ESR's then started to pull together designs that they had brought with them and developed them further within three groups that had formed naturally. During this early stage the staff leads held small advisory sessions with the groups with all teams having prototyped something, either at 1:1 or physical models by the end of day one. The designs at this stage progressed rapidly within most teams, having 3-7 designs being worked on at any one moment. This number gradually reduced, as day one drew to a close, with all groups settled on one design to take forward by the end of day one. From observation the main criteria for design survival process seemed to be the balance of aesthetic and ease of production. With groups that had more experience in fabrication allowing themselves to drift further from the more obvious.

DAY 2: Keep the Machines Moving:

If production is part of a design process then a balance needs to be struck, or more accurately, negotiated, between design and production time. No one would sensibly argue that it is of primary importance that the machines never stop producing, however useless the output. The other end of this spectrum can stall all output. The placing of this fulcrum will depend entirely on the process of establishing goals. This workshop attempted to place significant constraints on material, section size and manufacturing process with the intent of allowing a more in-depth exploration of the design to take place. Additional simplification and constraints

were created in the pathway to machining, so that the required part could be presented into the Rhino workspace and the Grasshopper plugin be automatically calculated and generated the Kuka tool path. No previous machining or robotics experience was required.

With such a significant reduction in options in design and production, the teams presented an array of design solutions to begin with. Simple, linear or circular arrays of assembled components became the most straightforward method of arriving at a structure quickly. The design process then became a focus on the module to be arrayed, the mechanics of interface with next iteration of itself, a possible progressive varying scale and the curating number offs and therefor-final arrangement. It was with such a process that some teams were able to arrive at a design that could go into production at a fairly early stage; it also enabled some to test the performance of the assembly through Finite Element Analysis (FEA).

The groups that held more experience in fabrication design and design for production were in a position to reject these “low hanging fruit” array-based solutions in search of something more refined, experimental and involved in their use of the tools and processes at hand. Enabled by certain material and process assumptions (a blend of accurate and inaccurate assumptions) and their computational, time and material costs, the designs evolved. One assumption that was less grounded was the gap between the decision-making process that existed for the Rhino workspace and that for the physical. There was a noticeable absence of material, joint and assembly performance criteria used as the design evolved, or where criteria were used, the designs operated so far away from the point where the material performance threshold would have implications. This became very apparent where some members or assemblies relied on sub 100-micron fit to occur to minimise compound error through a circular array, or a component that could never find its way into an assembly as there was no assembly sequence that would allow it. Some designs, when realised, proved to be unintended mechanisms, and other stiffening solutions proved unnecessary. A design fitness

function judgement in Rhino didn't always translate to the physical. Material strength was often brought below optimum in the resolution of a joint detail, and picked up as a problem in production.

An area that proved key, though unharnessed in this workshop, was part identification and part orientation once out of the Rhino workspace. The assembly components produced all looked very alike, a 50x50mm wooden section, of varying lengths, with square subtractions and 16mm holes. The teams labelled the parts, mating joints etc., but it was apparent that these designers and manufacturers found it a challenge to assemble the parts that they were the authors of: strangers to their own creations. Participants often held parts in their hands trying different fits, referencing the model on the screen. With each part having 6 definitions of freedom, the range of options that two known mates could be mated are extensive, and a lengthy trial and error process was the method engaged most. The embedding of physical part, position and pose data into the component geometry was discussed by the staff leads but not taken up by any of the teams.

DAY 3: Waiting for data:

In the introduction to this workshop, emphasis was placed on the very common scenario of experimental works around robotics, where the machines are always waiting for the code. As the robot sat idle, over most of day one and two, work on the designs carried on into the evening of day two, with only one team machining their components on the evening of day two. For the rest of the teams, the code was always "nearly there". This definition of "nearly there" is without doubt a perpetual, enquiring creative state, most commonly brought to conclusion or output through external influence. That is not to say that this style of enquiry will not resolve itself, or is without value, only that the heads working at the coal face of the enquiry need a nudge to consolidate their position and act. "We are, where we are."

So, from the very comfortable position of an observer, the final

outputs from the three teams were not so much a resolution, more a snapshot of what the team had achieved at the time of going to print. The value of output for each team sits in three areas: what the team is capable of; the potential of the provided technology given the teams capability; finally, how these systems of production can be adapted to allow greater outputs given user capability.

In conclusion, the greatest single observation was that despite the intentional integration of fabrication in the design process, production was seen as a separate event. Even within this small scale project, with as much manufacturing friction and material choice removed with the intention of aiding decision making and rapid design evolution, fabrication still, like most analogue and digital fabrications, played its role as a singularity event. Conclusions drawn after fabrication, which were then obvious to the teams, were unanticipated prior to the event. It would be easy to dismiss this as: process learning, craft is learning, first iteration, second iteration and the product improvement etc. However, observing this first hand it was clear that the users of the virtual workspace environment (Rhino in this instance) had placed expectations on the software to deliver all the information needed for basis of best decision making in the design pathway and production pathway.

This is certainly not a criticism of Rhino. Rhino is a sophisticated, accurate and powerful tool. If anything were to be criticised here it would be the handing over of full responsibility to a tool, without a clear understanding of the gaps it might or might not leave in a design process and realisation process. There is software that will assist in the simulation and emulation: Is it stable? Does it rock? Is it strong enough? There are rendering tools that will present it in certain lights, finishes or settings. Optimisation tools that will adjust joint configuration and member thickness, spacing etc. However, as humans, we start a new tier of judgement criteria once all of these have been satisfied, or, satisfied to within agreed practical constraints. Do I like it? This subjective area isn't without analytical problems but

that doesn't mean that there are not processes that in some way can investigate it.

One theme that was brought up from the beginning was to "fail as fast as possible." There is, within this context failing that we learn from and failing that stems from a known mistake. The latter adds limited value; the former is of huge importance. If there could be processes that we can carry out that, prior to fabrication that can give insights from a post-fabrication (or postproduction) perspective then these should be engaged with, or at least sought out. "What can I do, that will give me a greater understanding of how this will behave." Or "how will I feel about this afterwards, when it has been made". Model making, drawing and prototyping are all methods that are used successfully used to do this. These let us develop the design, but need a very focussed approach to describe the possible outputs from actual production processes. I would add that there are methods of using the tools of production more akin to a dress rehearsal that could prove useful. Film allows this: where the act of image capture is becoming more and more, the collection of raw material to be worked on back at the studio, post production, where the value of the final product isn't diluted by mass release. The realisation of architecture, and the impact on the architecture of the processes that made it, don't traditionally offer themselves up for postproduction processes. In dance, the process of dancers "marking" through choreography in order to rehearse and memorise is parallel to a process that would allow makers/users a view beyond the fabrication singularity event. This most certainly involves failing as fast as possible. To put so much energy into something that we could know will not yield fruit is an asset waste, the opposite to manufacturing processes that actively seeks faulty components in the production chain and remove them before they unnecessarily consume more valuable process resource.

On reflection: Without flippancy and acknowledging that the three groups worked diligently and beyond expectation over the three days,

I propose viewing this through two “laws” authored by Cyril Northcote Parkinson, known as (a) Parkinson’s law, that “the work expands so as to fill the time available for its completion”, and (b) Parkinson’s law of triviality, a disproportionate amount of time is spent working on the easier and more accessible work problems rather than issues that are less accessible, in need of greater abstraction to resolve but, have greater bearing on the final output.

If we can assume that the final physical output is the only output (admittedly, this disregards individual learning and development) and we understand this output through Parkinson’s law, then one could assume that the outputs at the end of day three could have been achieved at the end of day one. This isn’t an outrageous assumption. From observation, the design development from day one to three was disproportionate, in that what had been achieved from the morning of day one to the afternoon of day one wasn’t advanced proportionally over the additional two days. Given that the manufacturing process was automated and directly linked to design parameters that which was eventually sent to manufacture could have been sent much earlier in the process.

Understanding this to be true, and keeping the same constraints in place, how could this knowledge be used to assist in achieving a more significant output? And what aspects could benefit from the affordances of this understanding? If we look at this workshop through this understanding, (and this holds truths for many disciplines and work practices) the gains to be had in respect to the outputs of this workshop surely exist in the management of the advancement of designing for manufacture. One of the most valuable production assets in this workshop was time, and one, through goal driven management could significantly and positively impact the knowledge of the actual outputs of our tools of production.

FIG. Final result of the workshop showing two finished projects

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2.0 Scientific and Transferable Skill Courses

INTRODUCTION

The Scientific Courses are the second instrument of the Innochain scientific training provision, following the workshop-seminars. These are provided by the academic partners and include both technology-focussed teaching to provide the ESRs with the skills to creatively and critically engage with technology and theoretical courses that allow contextualisation.

Theory of Computation was held at the Bartlett and consisted of two days of lectures from leading experts in the fields of architecture and computation. These contextualised employed computational strategies and associated technologies for digital fabrication through an interdisciplinary understanding of the driving theories.

Robotic Steering and Control was held at IAAC and introduced robotic control protocols for design-based interfacing with special focus on tools for intuitive robot-CAD workflows. The taught aspect of the course led to group research projects that used clay extrusion as a vehicle for further technical development.

The Transferrable Skills Training Courses focus on implementation and innovation. The future courses will include topics such as project management, entrepreneurship and IP as well as personal career planning.

Academic Writing was held at KTH and online. It sharpened the ESRs' awareness of the underlying structure and patterns of scientific research articles and improved proficiency in writing-up research in English. Class preparation included the analysis of texts in course material and exercised focus on the problematic areas for academic writing for engineers and architects.

Theory of Computation

BSA (LONDON)
19 - 20 MAY 2016

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SCIENTIFIC COURSES

INTRODUCTION

This course introduced a range of different theories of computation and technology, each from a different practical, historical or philosophical point of view. It is intended to provide a framework in which innochain ESRs will be asked to consider their own position with respect to technology at a high level, and specifically to consider their work in the context of the three Innochain work packages in which ESRs are embedded. Course content was delivered in lecture format over a two full-day session in UCL on May 16-20, 2016, to which all ESRs were invited. Coursework was in the form of written essays submitted after this session.

Ten lectures were created specifically for this course by a combined group of Bartlett staff (7) and external, invited speakers (4). These were presented 19-20 May 2016:

- Frederic Migayrou: "Continuous and Discrete in computational Architecture"
- Mario Carpo: "The Second Digital Turn"
- Niloy Mitra: "Exploring Design Variations"

FIG. LEFT PAGE Amalgama by Rodriguez A., Camilleri F., Doukhi N. and Strukov R. Bartlett Wonderlab 2015

FIG. RIGHT PAGE Innochain participants attending dedicated the lecture series

- Peter Scully: "Computation or emulation? Can digital manufacturing be more than automation.?"
- Robert Aish: "Design Computation"
- Sean Hanna: "AI and Design"
- Alisa Andrasek: "Exponential Design"
- Fiona Zisch: "The Mental Representation and Simulation of Space"
- Stephen Gage: "The Properties of Aesthetically Potent Environments in a Digital Age"
- Bob Sheil and Nick Callicot: "Reflections on Making"

During the preceding three days, 16-18 May, some ESRs attended the 7th annual Symposium on Simulation for Architecture and Urban Design (SimAUD), hosted at UCL, in which 37 paper presentations were given. This exposed ESRs further to current work in progress internationally and provided a forum for networking and discussing with the academic field.

Thirteen of the fifteen Innochain ESRs attended the lecture series in person, with one absence due to personal circumstances. The ten lectures created for the course were video recorded and edited for distribution online, to be available to all Innochain participants and eventually to the wider public.

Coursework was a written essay in which ESRs were asked to address, in the context of one or more of the lectures above, how their own work challenges the existing discourse in how design is communicated, how simulation is used in design, and how design is materialised. This submission was coordinated with the INNOCHAIN Transferrable Skills Course on Academic Writing, at KTH on 7-10 June, 2016; in many cases the essay was completed with input from this course, and a single essay of 2000-3000 words was submitted for both courses. Six ESRs submitted under this format, after attending both courses. Due to the varied training schedules of ESRs across the Innochain project, essays will continue to be accepted for credit in the project second year. The combined workload of this course is worth 3.5 ECTS.

FIG. Exposure by Anthony Gormley, ©Iain Masterton

Theory of Computation paper

Digital tools beyond aesthetics: mass creativity and the enablement of emergence

Dimitrie A. Stefanescu

ESR NUMBER: ESR05
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Henn GmbH
INSTITUTE: BSA

INTRODUCTION

Digital design tools are now undergoing a transition of application scope, expanding beyond their initial technical domains and leveraging the flexibility of the digital medium - in which they exist - to its fullest extent.

Digital means of communication are enabling the self-organisation of new cultures as well as decision-making structures revolving around the possibilities inherent to the digital realm. Design tools are slowly catching up - to a certain extent - by building upon the flexibility of parametric design in order to improve the communication channels of the design process, thus signalling the achievement of a certain "digital maturity" of the architectural design community.

Unfortunately, the current state of collaborative design software is catering exclusively to the needs of the technical stakeholders involved in the design and building process, namely architects, engineers and builders. In our contemporary world, where social change and action is not only supported but triggered by digital communication tools, the design disciplines stand to lose credibility

if they will not take initiative and tap into the existing expectations of collaboration that today's society now harbours.

The following paper puts forward a new research direction for the design of digital tools that aims to investigate ways in which to make the design process more open and approachable by non-technical stakeholders. A design never exists independently from the tools that are used in its creation and vice versa. As such, it is important to note that this entails both a technological development effort as well as the elaboration of a methodological package that supports the meaningful usage of said tools - essentially an active tectonic study that manifests as an accelerated feedback loop between both tool and process development.

STRUCTURE

In the first section we put forward the concept of mass creativity as an extension of mass collaboration. Within this context we introspectively define the role of an architect as a translator between the various interests of the stakeholders involved in the design process. The second section subsequently looks at the tools that a designer has at hand to accomplish this role. We critically analyse

the notational paradigm upon which contemporary digital tools are based on and outline both their disadvantages and strengths that can be speculated. Following this, the third section concerns itself with outlining a case study which reveals how a different approach to using digital design tools – one that renounces the classical notational paradigms – can be applied. Two more similar examples are outlined in the fourth section in support of “de-aesthetised” digital design. We subsequently conclude by acknowledging the importance of creating digital tools and methodologies that support the designer in fostering the emergence of mass creativity, thus responding to one of the main challenges of today.

A CASE FOR MASS CREATIVITY

Collaboration has become embedded within today’s design environment as projects are no longer the result of an isolated creation process, but an emergence of a myriad of interactions between various human and non-human actors. Architects, engineers, banks, communities, politicians and various other animate and quasi-inanimate agents contribute towards the final embodiment of a specific design and its subsequent evolution.

As such, we can justly state that the built environment is, at a global level, an emergent feature that results from countless interactions of material and social flows. Extrapolating further, there is no fundamental difference to speak of between the laws that govern the processes that give birth to cultural artefacts, and those of natural artefacts: they both share the same generative principles loosely aggregated under the umbrella term of “emergence”.

The contemporary new materialist school of thought, spearheaded by science and technology studies and anthropology, have gone further and argued for the dissolution of the Modern dichotomy between Nature and Culture [1], [2]. Furthermore, the concept of a static, finite, encapsulated object is no longer valid. In its place we now observe the emergence of large-scale patterns from the interactions

of various flows of matter-energy. Bruno Latour calls them quasi-objects: objects that are only defined by their web of interactions - a conglomeration of threads representing process flows that give birth to recognisable features [3]. These ideas lend themselves well to aspects of computational design that we shall elaborate on in the following section.

One of the most powerful implications of this "non-modern" context is that we, as designers, are part of the swarm of decision makers whose actions lead to the crystallisation of the built environment. Our creativity and contribution to the development of a project is equally valuable as that of all the other stakeholders involved in the process, both animate and inanimate.

What seems initially to be a harmless statement of the status quo becomes a game changer if properly embedded into the rationale of design methodologies: it entails a redefinition of the architect's scope of action and role. To a certain extent this has always been the case - nevertheless by centring the above statement as the core of the designer's position we do raise the need to adapt both the methodologies that we apply when designing as well as the tools we are using to communicate and enact that respective design. The role of the architect as "master builder" is no longer feasible due to its scope which, within the contemporary practice, expands to unsustainable dimensions.

Nevertheless, one can argue that the designer - within the group of stakeholders associated with a project - has a polarising position because he needs to process information flows coming from a wide array of sources: architectural, economical, social, etc. This does not translate to a position of control, as "classical" architectural education would teach us - it is a position of greater responsibility. If we define a design project as an emergent feature from the interactions of various agents, then the architect's main role is thus revealed as being the facilitator of meaningful interactions between all the relevant stakeholders. Consequently, the designer is a conduit of communication, constantly translating between the languages

of expression of the various stakeholders involved in the project, including his own. Among the many languages spoken we find, for example, financial analysts talking in future values and internal rate of returns, engineers articulating finite element analyses that evaluate a design for its structural consistency, local communities voicing their ideas in social terms that do not lend themselves easily to quantification, and so on.

Essentially, an important point to acknowledge is that all stakeholders are creative. For example, the financial design that enables the project to be built embodies the same qualities as the innovative concept that the designer brought to the table. The expression of this creativity takes various forms and is not universally translatable across different groups without active effort. Ideally, the design process is not one of just mass collaboration, but one of mass creativity that results from a harmonious negotiation process.

DESIGN TOOLS & ARCHITECTURAL NOTATION

The means of communication and tools an architect has access to need to enable the expression of creativity from all involved stakeholders. In such a diverse environment, as usually is coagulated around contemporary design projects, the lack of good communication channels and/or the inability to translate between disciplines and interest groups usually leads to friction, dissatisfaction and compromised results.

Classical architectural notation, developed by Alberti in the 15th century, has focused on developing identical copies between the design of the building (virtual) and its embodiment in reality (construction) [4]. Plans, sections, elevations, and so on, are essentially schematic notations that encode architectural information into a language that is controlled by a certain set of standards. As such, one can design, communicate and build within a single system.

Digital design tools have evolved as analogues of the same paradigm

as classical architectural notation, their main goal being that of making identical copies of the information that they encode. For example, Ivan Sutherland's Sketchpad program, considered the precursor to all CAD software, was essentially a digital drafting tool: it replaces the draftsman's traditional pen with a "light-pen" and paper with "digital" paper. As such, we can argue that the notational mechanisms of today are identical to that of classical architectural script, which has remained unchanged since the Renaissance. To this day, all architectural drafting software is essentially a direct transposition of Albertian notational principles into the digital medium. Another notable evolutionary step in the design of digital tools is that of the increased linkage with fabrication techniques and construction site management. By weaving together building and material constraints, digital tools have greatly expanded the geometrical vocabulary that is now accessible to the designer. This movement, which began in the early 1990s, has been appraised as "The Digital Revolution". In its first stage it negated the principles of mass production and standardisation by introducing a new formal agenda based upon the new found expression liberties offered by the "isolated" digital medium [5].

This leads us to the second stage of the digital revolution in architectural design; going beyond mass customisation, by speculating the qualities of the "connected" digital medium. In this way, we would argue for the transition to mass collaboration and, subsequently, to mass creativity, thus empowering the contemporary design process – one in which every stakeholder is creative and is able to define value.

In the past, exploration of variation was limited due to the friction of the analogue medium (pen and paper) in which architecture was expressing itself. The virtual realm has effectively eliminated this barrier and thus paved the way for a comprehensive exploration of the "objectile" (or quasi-object) [1]. Software like Grasshopper or Dynamo enable the architect to no longer be author objects, but

processes whose result is not a single finite object, but, as mentioned above, quasi-objects, or families of objects. Various performance measures – feasibility, material constraints, etc. – usually act as selection criteria which collapse the object into a single object that is subsequently built.

Here we have to make a technical distinction between the “isolated” digital and the “connected” digital. Current digital design tools rely mostly on the qualities of the “isolated” digital medium, i.e. embodied in a single technological unit: the designer’s computer.

Collaboration is achieved by packaging finite designs and exchanging them via emails or other surrogate management systems. The connected digital medium - i.e., the internet - offers a wildly different set of qualities that are yet to be integrated and repurposed for the use within design process.

Generalising, the current Albertian notational paradigm does not address the need for a flexible and interchangeable language that would allow the designer to enact his negotiator role. While being extremely efficient for aesthetic and technical exploration, digital tools still structure communication in a non-agile way that is focused on describing the “final” object. The vocabulary it uses is not always flexible enough in order to be articulated in an accessible way for all stakeholders, both technical and non-technical.

CASE STUDY: PROBLEM & CONTEXT

When we are faced with a set of tools for a linear process, for instance, packaging a finished design to email to a client, the space for unexpected encounters (emergent possibilities) is narrowed, forcing a design environment that lacks in dialog. Non-technical stakeholders (communities, financial analysts, government authorities, etc.) are not yet integrated in the (digital) design chain - on the contrary, current practice usually positions them in an adversarial role and does not allow them to exceed their pre-assigned conflictual position due to the limitations of existing design tools and methodologies.

This problem manifested itself during the development of a feasibility study for a future large-scale urban development in the heart of Brussels, the “traditional” design approach failed and a new, flexible design process had to be developed and communicated in order to meaningfully respond to the questions posed by the assignment. This study was undertaken by the author while employed at Bogdan & Van Broeck, an architectural consultancy and design office based in Brussels. Specifically, the assignment called for an exploration of the possible directions in which a large site owned by the Flemish Government could evolve within the context of a PPP (public-private partnership) development. Initially the brief required an investigation into the functions that would meaningfully fit on the given site coupled with volumetric explorations on various organisational principles that would accommodate the given proposed functional

FIG. LEFT Initial Excel model: developed with REBEL Group

FIG. RIGHT Final application: a cross-platform app was developed

programmes.

The main stakeholder groups involved in the project consisted of The Flemish Government (VO), The Developers and Private Investors and, finally, The Policy Makers. Bogdan & Van Broeck, as the office in charge of elaborating the study, was situated as a mediator between all three parties. When the initial outline of the study was being formulated, the traditional approach was failing due to the fact that the representational means were not adapted to the interests of the stakeholders that had vested interests in the project. "Classical" architectural notation and drawings, while being seductive and incorporating a great amount of information in an efficiently small package, were not embodying the right message and were forcing a specific approach that was destabilising the design process.

With hindsight, we can say that the main problem was the language used to communicate and synthesize the decisions being taken. Urban and architectural plans, coupled with textual descriptions, were not versatile enough to translate between the interests of all the involved parties. For example, variations of the masterplan were proposed in a traditional form, with schematic drawings. These were coupled with textual descriptions that presented social implications and financial outlooks that emerged from the design process.

While initially an unassuming presentation mode, this was triggering The Flemish Government's representatives to request more detailed and eye-catching designs, while the policy makers were increasingly sceptical due to the apparent lack of "substance" that the increasingly realistic presentation drawings were making. At the same time, the developers were becoming convinced of the fact that the proposals were not actually financially feasible due either to their too "glossy" nature or due to their too high "socially-aware" functions. This led to the development of mistrust between the involved parties, subsequently halting the design process.

While the proposed solutions were, essentially, the embodiment of the negotiations between all stakeholders involved, they were not revealing the inner mechanics of the synthesizing process that we were undertaking. The negotiation process required to develop the proposed scenarios was not visible – even if value was defined taking into account the priorities of all stakeholders, it was not collaboratively defined. As such, consensus was impossible to reach: the three parties involved did not understand each other's priorities and what impact they have on the other's set of parameters.

To sum up, the stakeholders did not speak the same language. Classical architectural notation, based on the representational

FIG. LEFT Parameters were split into two main categories: global financial assumptions and functional percentages

FIG. RIGHT Information flow reveals a dynamic structure

paradigm, was not enough to enable communication between the project's actors – on the contrary, we can argue that, because it was forcing the designers to present “finite” objects/geometry, it was detrimental to the design process.

CASE STUDY: RESOLUTION

We realised that the value of the feasibility study we were elaborating lay not in the actual finite designs that we were delivering, but in the processes of communication and translation that we were undertaking. As such, we decided to package the negotiation process itself into a deliverable tool by creating a simulacrum of a “dj mixer” that will allow intuitive control of relevant parameters, provide users with direct feedback regarding choices and be relevant to all stakeholder groups, regardless of their background. This was achieved by developing, together with a financial consultancy firm, a parametric model that took into account architectural, urban and, most importantly, financial parameters (figure 1). Subsequently, this model was transformed into an interactive negotiation application that was made accessible to the extended group of stakeholders as a base for negotiation (figure 2).

During the development and (brief) testing of the application, several important aspects were revealed as being critical. First, the categorisation and selection of parameters played a crucial role in alleviating the “paradox of choice”: when confronted with a wealth of modifiable inputs, the users were unable to reach a satisfactory solution. As such, reducing the parameters to the minimum – without sacrificing any critical ones – was instrumental to reach the increased accessibility levels desired. Second, the inner logic of the model was hidden from the end-users. Parametric models can be daunting to the non-expert, and, subsequently, discourage them from their usage. This resulted, in isolated cases, in a diminishing of trust in the calculations being performed. Nevertheless, this negative aspect was outweighed by the fact that previously non-technical stakeholders, previously shy but expressing a strong passive discontent, were now willing to approach and join the conversation due to their new-found

empowerment. Their inclusion was instrumental to unblocking the design process.

Third, and most importantly, we emphasized the flow of information by graphically displaying the links between all relevant parameters and their implications (figure 4).

This allowed the stakeholders to understand and grasp the implications of their preferences with regard to the others' definitions of value (and profit). A global understanding of the system resulted: all actors involved in the design process were finally aware of each others' priorities and ways of thinking. It was through this distributed global understanding of quality and value that the proceedings were unblocked. Essentially, the study's main value revealed itself in the creation of the aforementioned sense of understanding between the stakeholders.

FIG. TOP PARTIAL interface and design evaluation

FIG. BOTTOM PARTIAL performance profile of the participant's design compared with a self-referential frameset

BEYOND AESTHETICS

Up to now, the flexibility of the digital medium has been leveraged purely for the aesthetic exploration and technical optimisation of designs which, ultimately, are collapsed into one “single” or “final” solution. Nevertheless, we strongly believe that, to a certain extent, digital tools can now go beyond aesthetics. How can digital tools go beyond aesthetics and help the designer in his role as a conduit of communication? We have presented above one example of how a parametric model can act as a translation tool between the various languages employed by a specific set of stakeholders, both technical and non-technical.

Another recent example can be found in the work of Dominik Holzer and Steven Downing, DesignLink [6]. The authors propose “optioneering” as a design methodology that encourages “a form of discourse where design partners negotiate the criteria space for a design problem at the outset of their collaboration” [6]. Coupled with DesignLink, a software specifically developed to enable this kind of high-frequency collaboration, albeit amongst technical stakeholders only.

An outstanding example of using digital tools as a communication instrument that leverages collaborative design principles can be found in the work of R. Aish and J. Fleming from 1977 (Robert Aish, 1977). The authors devised a parametric computer aided design system (PARTIAL) geared towards defining a context in which both professional designers (architects) and end-users can collaboratively design and evaluate a particular building type. The authors’ intention was to “provide a context where the designers/ participants could combine their own subjective design ideas with the necessary technical requirements” [7]. The research presented by the authors is from a time when the “connected” digital medium (the internet) didn’t exist yet in a form that was accessible to all, or, for that matter, had a

name. Nevertheless, it shows great foresight by aiming to enable all participants to “operate directly on [...] a complex, multivariate, but nevertheless, extremely real decision making process” through the use of digital design tools.

Enabling participation and, through which allowing for the emergence of mass creativity, should be a key driver in the development of future design tools. Non-technical stakeholders must be included in order for one to be able to properly define value in a collaborative manner. “Quality” can mean one thing for the developer and a completely different thing for the designer, and hold yet another meaning for the surrounding community. As such, digital design tools must start to respond to the need of communication and translation between various stakeholders.

CONCLUSION

Today’s society is expected to be digitally involved: from Facebook and Twitter enabling social change to platforms such as Github (which allows anyone with the right skills to creatively contribute to the development of a software project), Peer-to-Peer networks and Bitcoin (a digital currency which exists as decentralised entity on all its users’ connected computers), and so on and so forth – the examples are endless.

Bringing together the non-modern context in which the design disciplines currently stand with the realities of the business environment reveals a complex web of interaction that requires careful articulation and negotiation. Creativity is not an isolated phenomenon under the exclusive rights of the designer, but a distributed quality that emerges from numerous interactions. As such, the role of the designer is transcending its simplistic understanding of “master builder” towards a “master negotiator” and an enabler of meaningful interactions.

It is in this context that, in order for a project to go forward, value

needs to be defined collaboratively and as a shared sense amongst all the involved stakeholders. Current communication methods that are available to the architect rely on a notation that does not fully cater to these needs, and, as explained in the case study, sometimes can hinder it. Designers need to be able to orchestrate “a positive and spontaneous co-creative and emergent process” [8]

Digital tools have inherent qualities that have yet to be purposed towards these applications. We are already no longer designing finite objects, but rather processes that give birth to a set of objects. These “objectiles” are only defined by their network of interactions – of which, we, as designers, are in control.

Digital parametric models can go beyond aesthetic and technical exploration: they can embody a narrative and subsequently be the base of collaborative decision making. The flexibility of computational design can and should be used outside the architectural office and its technical collaborators. Nevertheless, we would like to end on a note of caution: “the choice of representation affects the process of design and should be understood prior to the creation and use of intelligent computational systems” [9] Tools can be used for good or for bad: a hammer can be used to build a house or to destroy an ancient statue, social media can be used to organise a legitimate protest or manipulate people towards dubious causes. The responsibility of articulating a meaningful design is still in the hands of the agents enabling it to happen.

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Theory of Computation paper

Digital Craftsmanship: On the Pursuit of Craftsmanship within Digital Fabrication Technologies

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In the last decades digital fabrication technologies , such as CNC machines and robotic arms, moved outside the industrial setting for mass production, where they were originally developed [1], to be increasingly adopted within design-driven practices. For designers, the accessibility to these tools represents an opportunity to reconnect their practice to the physical dimension of fabrication and give form to a series of design speculations confined, until now, behind the computer's screen.

The possibility of maintaining the control over the entire digital workflow, from the initial design intention to the final product, coincides de facto with an extension of the role of the designer itself, which for centuries has been progressively detached from the realm of construction [2]. The newly acquired central role of "making" within these new practices suggests the intention to separate themselves from a specialised industrial configuration, moving toward a more holistic design dimension that finds one of its main references in traditional human craftworks, which nowadays seem to be addressed with rejuvenated interest.

Within this discourse, the overly abused term “digital craftsmanship” indicates the aspiration of combining the latest fabrication technologies with more traditional ways of making, which are not contemplated, at least not always, in a nostalgic dimension but rather as inspiring references for novel manufacturing processes. However, there are arguably three critical aspects in this transition that still remain unresolved, suggesting that this aspired combination has not happened yet.

The first aspect regards the process of abstraction needed to encapsulate a design into a notational form to translate it to a machine. This implies that all the data necessary to fabricate an artefact are possible to be explicitly stated, transmitted and processed, while no relevant information is lost in this translation. However, in traditional human craftworks there is clearly a tacit dimension that is difficult to capture, formalise and share [3] and this type of knowledge, which drives the creation of any artefact, is acquired through “observation, induction and participation rather than formal inquiry” [4], [5].

As suggested by N. Callicott, representational means in design

practices are attempts to translate part of this knowledge into an explicit formulation in order to be shared, however this information exchange via graphical means results very often incomplete and too approximate. On the other hand, the numerically- controlled (N/C) paradigm was conceived as a system to circumvent the challenge of bringing the contribution of this tacit dimension into digital fabrication processes [6]. Every machine operation is explicitly defined with an original scripting and it doesn't need to relate to any external source of information, everything is computed based on the prescribed internal logic of the system. This is achieved through an abstraction, and inevitable simplification, of the variables involved in both the fabrication process and in the geometry to be fabricated. As a consequence of this reduction logic, it's possible to use only materials that are homogeneous enough to be abstracted into a notation, with known properties that could be written down into tables. Any material agency has to be neglected or overwritten in order to avoid possible deviations from the geometric notation [7].

The second critical aspect is the lack of active information and feedback loops among the different stages of the digital workflow which results in a linearly organised manufacturing process where the moment of design is distinctly separated from the fabrication stage.

While a craftsman initiates a task with only a preconception of the intended object/process and the design unfolds together with the fabrication of the artefact, the digital maker operates within a highly constrained one-directional workflow where it is necessary to incorporate all the necessary information in a CAD/CAM model before the fabrication stage [4]. Once the CNC tools have been set up and launched, it's not possible to intervene anymore in the production process, which becomes a sequential execution of pre-calculated machine's trajectories. On the other hand, the under-constrained fabrication setting in traditional craftworks, which allows interactivity and exploration, is made possible by a dense exchange

of information among the brain and body of the craftsman, the tool in his hands and the material being processed. If everything would need to be precomputed before moving to the fabrication as it happens in current digital manufacturing processes, not only this would limit the range of variability that the system could potentially address, but it would negate completely the generative dimension present in the process of “making”.

The third critical aspect is the lack of a temporal dimension within digital fabrication processes, which result to be static frameworks unable to adapt, evolve and improve under specific contingencies. While you can expect a machine to perfectly reproduce thousands of times the same object, you can't expect the machine to improve the same amount of times after each iteration as a human craftsman would do. Indeed, every time a craftsman produces an artefact, this coincides with a reorganisation of his individual tacit knowledge that initiates the task. This ability to learn over time leads to the development of personal skills which allow him to create a unique artefact increasingly well after each iteration [9].

After the Second World War, the main driving reason for the development of digitally controlled production systems was to give a universal answer to the challenge of automatically producing, and even more important reproducing, any given geometry, moving beyond the need of individual skillsets and specific configurations [8]. On the other hand, the strength of traditional craftworks finds place in their specific and subjective dimension, which allows to continuously adapt and evolve the fabrication process in response to temporal contingencies related to a specific design brief, different selection of tools and skillsets and unique material behaviours.

As presented by the historian D. Noble, parallel to the development of N/C paradigm in US, there have been an attempt to capture this subjective dimension of making to answer the same need of generating information for automatic production and this is represented by the

Record/Playback paradigm (R/L), developed in the 1940s by General Electric (Noble, 1984). Within this system, a machinist was able to operate a modified machine tool to produce an artefact and get the totality of his motions recorded on a magnetic tape which could be automatically reproduced later by the machine. In those recorded motion was captured not only the gears' mechanical displacement but also the machinist's intelligence, skills and tacit knowledge [9]. As observed by N. Callicott "Record/Playback comprised a deliberate attempt to distribute the tacit knowledge of a select group of individuals into an automated system, effectively replacing it with explicit and repeatable rules" [6]. The intelligence of the production system was still coming from to the human that operates the machine though, diminishing the authority of managerial control over the production process, in contrast with N/C systems developed with the opposite intention of detaching the workers on the shop floor from the design process [9].

Beside the social and political implications, the technical bottleneck of R/L paradigm appears to be in the same specificity that the system aims to capture: the recorded information of a past moment could only be used to reproduce a new instance of the same object in the future. Indeed, machine tools configurations, processed materials and geometric information must remain the same, while if any major change needed to be done, it was necessary to perform another machinist's recording from the beginning. The system was conceived to capture one single consistent event, but it was not able to compare this with others and generalise the captured information to extend its potential application. In this regard, the N/C system results, despite the overall abstraction and simplification, more versatile since the same fabrication logic could be seamlessly adapted to infinite variations of an artefact within given solution boundaries.

In the light of the technological advancements in control systems, it seems finally possible to move beyond the opposing aspirations of universality that belongs to the N/C paradigm and of uniqueness

of traditional craftworks that R/L paradigm attempted to capture, combining both aspects in a novel paradigm for digital manufacturing. In a framework where the designer is directly involved in the act of “making”, it’s necessary to envision more intuitive ways how he/she could engage with the fabrication process: is it possible to train a robot how to perform a task rather than programming it line-by-line? The challenge remains, like after the Second World War, mostly conceptually in finding ways of generating information that could drive the machine rather than in the technological means themselves, which in the case of industrial robotic arms have been around for decades without any major change.

With nowadays sensing technology (e.g. 3d scanning, motion capture systems, force-torque sensors...etc), is possible to record with a high degree of precision the sequence of actions performed by a human during a specific task together with the combination of fabrication parameters involved. Recorded data could be subsequently manipulated and processed to playback the same task with the machine alone or even used to directly control it alongside in real-time. In this way, it’s possible to instruct a machine about a given task without programming it line-by-line but directly demonstrating how to perform it. While directly instructing by demonstration is particularly relevant to industrial automation where a robotic arm has to repeat that very specific motion trajectory thousands of times, such a system falls back in the constraining specificity and uniqueness of the original R/L paradigm, which was not able to adapt to different configurations necessities in a design-driven environment. What is missing is the ability by the fabrication system to outline the relevant parameters and the definition of recurrent pattern within the task: the robot repeats, but it doesn’t learn, therefore it could not adapt to any other, even slightly, different configuration.

To move beyond this stage, instead of recording only a single fabrication iteration of a specific artefact, it is possible to record and store multiple sessions of similar fabrication tasks, associated by

common parameters (e.g. same type of material or set of tools), that allow to obtain an overall understanding of a fabrication process rather than the making of a specific shape. Identifying the relevant fabrication parameters (e.g. tool angle, actuation force, material/tool interaction... etc) and determining their digital quantification, beyond the simple motion trajectory, become a crucial moment to capture meaningful aspects of the tacit knowledge involved in the "making".

However, this tacit dimension, which multiple recordings aim to capture, is not found in a specific recorded parameter, nor in few recorded samples of the same task, but it rather lies in the totality of the collected fabrication data and their combinations through multiple iterations in time. As humans, we are not able to process a vast amount of information as numbers: the recorded dataset remains immeasurable and tacit since we are not able to extract relevant patterns that would help us structure the knowledge in order to make it explicit and possible to communicate.

Machine learning processes, for instance Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), were conceived to address exactly this kind of issue, becoming a very valuable tool in the perspective of teaching a robot an adaptive fabrication skillset rather than a specific motion trajectory. ANN, loosely inspired by their biological equivalent, could be described as layered and interconnected networks of "neurons", "which process information by their dynamic state response to external inputs" [10]. Within a supervised learning process for instance, the ANN could be trained with a dataset of fabrication parameters recorded through multiple sessions and compute the interrelated logic among these parameters to subsequently inform, in a new "unseen" configuration, the robotic fabrication process. In this way, the designer won't have to write down beforehand the parameters governing the machine actuation, but he would be able to work with a fabrication tool that has been trained to take informed decisions at each step. Ironically, the combination of fabrication parameters recording and learning process to instruct a machine coincides with a deeper understanding

on our side about the complexity of human making, discovering unseen relations that were tacitly transmitted through years of practice but were difficult to grasp and quantify.

Such a learning system finds its fulfilment not in the initial training stage, but rather in its unfolding within a given fabrication task while being informed by active information and feedback loops about the fabrication setup, environment conditions, material behaviours and design intentions. This information becomes the “unseen” configuration against which the trained network is utilised, determining the adaptive actuation response: the moment of design blurs completely with the fabrication stage, reciprocally informing each other. The information acquired through the feedback loops is not only used to perform that specific fabrication task but it is also stored and compiled in a fabrication dataset used by the ANN to keep learning and to improve at each iteration even after the initial training stage. Within this framework, simulation is not used beforehand as a predictive tool to project assumptions from the digital to the physical world but the other way around to compile the incoming stream of sensor information in an updating digital interface that allows the designer to maintain control over the fabrication process and intervene at any time to adjust it. In the last stage of its development, the learning and feedback-driven fabrication process becomes indeed a framework to foster the collaboration between the human and the machine. The designer operates within a system that is flexible and able to receive feedback, not only from fabrication parameters, but also from the human counterpart. Because of this, the fabrication framework is open toward the interaction of both human and machine on the artefact being produced, enhancing each other skills, and obtaining a result that would have not been possible with only one of the two parts alone.

In this way, the explorative dimension of the design process is extended to the fabrication stage, thanks to an under-constrained environment that is flexible, adaptable and that could learn, becoming

a framework where humans and machines could actively collaborate in a novel design partnerships, finally achieving together a true “digital craftsmanship”.

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Theory of Computation: Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS

Through review of the submitted papers it is clear that the exercise of theoretical reflection on the initial research positions successfully encouraged the ESRs to recast the original Innochain research questions into an agenda for which they take personal responsibility. As such, it provided a valuable service both to the framing of the research itself and to the ESR's own development. This is attested to by informal feedback from ESRs and by the quality and breadth of the currently submitted essays. Several of these will be considered for academic publication externally to the Innochain project and will form some of the required documentation for PhD review procedures within the partner universities.

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Academic Writing

COMING TO WRITING - THE CRITICAL ART OF
WRITTEN EXPRESSION
KTH (STOCKHOLM)
07 - 10 JUNE 2016

Led by Helene Frichot (KTH)

INTRODUCTION

The Innochain Academic Writing seminar sought to give research students within the InnoChain network the opportunity to critically understand the implications of how they present their work through academic and non-academic writing. Participants were encouraged to extend their practice of writing beyond the conventional academic norm that is supposed to objectively and transparently account for a research problem. The tasks and exercises undertaken in the seminar allowed for alternative approaches to writing, commencing from the idea that writing is a practice that needs to be developed in critical and creative alignment with the content of a research project.

The workshop progressed over four days from the 7th to 10th of June. Each day was dedicated to a specific writing task, which was then discussed during the seminar. These tasks enabled students to experiment with a variety of modes of writing, from the academic abstract, to the popular science essay, to the use of Web 2.0 formats, as a way of extending an engagement in contemporary information technologies and plain language formats. Participants concluded the course with plans toward the writing of a peer reviewed journal article, which would be composed following the style guidelines of a scientific journal of their own choosing. Finally, as an acknowledgement of the Gender Support document prepared by InnoChain with the stated aim of achieving adequate gender representation of ‘men and women’ in the ‘digital chain’, participants were requested to cite a diversity of references in their peer review article, specifically making sure not to exclude the work of women scholars and practitioners, and being alert to where other minority groups might be called on when searching for references to support their arguments.

Academic writing paper

Material communication in computationally-driven timber practice (and vice versa)

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INTRODUCTION

It is by now undeniable that the advent of ubiquitous computing tools has changed the way architectural design is considered and carried out. Embedded digital technology has so completely pervaded everyday life that it has become second nature, and the design of artefacts and buildings has definitely not been immune to this shift. This has, of course, opened up new worlds of concepts, tools, terminologies, applications, theories, and so on, which bring with them their own particular advantages and baggage. Formal languages have emerged, driven by functions and algorithms, and ways of systematising and understanding our environment in obsessive detail have been developed and put into practice. These days, this is nothing new. From the early use of CAD and CAM in universities to the condition now where computer-aided-everything forms a core part of architectural industry and practice, digital design tools - computation and parametric models - have arrived and are here to stay.

However, what has not yet emerged, or, rather, what is still the subject of intense speculation and research as the field slowly matures, is

how this relationship between computational tools and the actual practice of making architecture should unfold. This is most likely due to the incredible diversity and number of possible applications of computation within all the different nooks and crannies of architectural practice - from formal development, to structural optimization, to logistics scheduling and assembly planning, and so on - so it is likely that there will never be a single dominating framework or method for what is loosely grouped together and referred to as 'digital design'. Computational tools instead find themselves tailored and deployed in ways that are particular to each practice or field, often in a very invisible way.

What can be gleaned from a quick survey of architectural design and/or research practices which engage with computation, however, is that despite their wildly different focuses and modes of working, common themes do re-appear after all. Two themes - quite closely related, actually - tend to appear consistently: the changing relationship of the architect/designer with digitally- driven tools of production - that is, how computational practice is changing the way in which architectural artefacts are made and the role of the designer within the actual making - and the pursuit of the understanding and integration of material behaviour and performance into the design of these artefacts. Although it can be easily argued that material performance has always been a fundamental aspect of making architecture, the difference is that these computational tools now allow for a much deeper and nuanced understanding of material behaviour - a higher resolution and more direct links to iterative patterns of design - and this understanding is being used to instigate designs and reveal new solutions, rather than to just serve them.

To understand this playing field better, there needs to be an understanding of how these themes and relationships are being conceptualized, how the made artefact is both modelled and made to emerge from these concepts, and how the consequences of these developments are making their way into practice - both research and

industry. From all the different material systems, tools, and possible architectural objectives available, the discussion will mostly focus on timber practices, while at the same time recognizing that this subject cannot be interrogated in isolation from other parallel material systems and practices. The aim of this discussion is to construct a framework for a research project which is concerned with the integration of material performance of glue-laminated timber assemblies - between multi-disciplinary architectural practice and industrial engineered timber fabrication - and thereby create a point of departure for further inquiry.

FRAMEWORKS

There are several relevant methodologies or frameworks here, and they will be described and discussed from the broad application to design and research practice to more timber and tool-specific ways of thinking about architectural design.

The first indicates a larger conceptual shift across architectural design towards a material focus and a materially-based application of computation. It recognizes that the currency of architecture is design, that its medium is physical material, and therefore its knowledge-generating capabilities must be grounded in material practice. Practice-based research has emerged as a viable research method in many fields [1] [14], but it finds a special resonance with how architectural knowledge is produced [13] since making and physical prototyping form such an important part of the architect's vocabulary. The proliferation of computational tools has augmented the understanding of making and materials, therefore this approach binds the two together, promoting a computational understanding of material behaviours and a material demonstration of computational modelling.

This sort of material-computation interplay and feedback also forms the basis for a newer paradigm, coined 'fabrication information modeling' or FIM [2]. This framework confronts the divide between

digital design tools and making, and proposes a methodology that addresses geometry at multiple scales, fabrication and material parameters, and a trans-disciplinary exchange of data. It is a kind of implementation of practice-based research in architecture and attempts to clarify specific requirements and core concepts. In this way, it both broadens the practice-led approach by opening up the design process to include other fields and makes it more specific by requiring it to work across various scales. Though this may happen anyway simply by virtue of the different scales present in any material assembly - material, element, structure - FIM further demands an integration across those scales. What the method also reiterates is the importance of the tool and the importance of designing directly with the realities of fabrication. In fact, FIM argues for an iterative ground-up design path, beginning with the specifics of the material and the tool, and meeting the design in the middle.

This interface with the tools of production is articulated in a reconsideration of the role of the architect / designer. Computation has brought design and fabrication much closer together in terms of the medium they inhabit: the software used to design and represent architecture is very similar to the software used to program and drive multi-axis machining centres. They share a common language of curves, surfaces, work-planes, and coordinates. This reintroduction of production tools within the same space as design tools means that the two can be dealt with side-by-side, using similar design logic and approach. The architect with his digital tools is seen as reconstituting the traditional role of craftsman and master builder, and therefore design and making becomes a 'digital craftsmanship'

FIG. The discrete steps that fabrication information modeling addresses. FIM is meant to change this directed sequence into a bidirectional one incorporating feedback and iterative development between each step

[7]. The control which the architect is now able to exercise over the physical artefact presumably opens up new and more intelligent designs, but it also requires the architect to become deeply familiar with the process of making.

To bring the discussion around to a material-specific context, this new digitally-enabled resurgence of craft is traced through the development of timber processing technologies. The roles of energy, material, and information have evolved through three eras or 'ages' in wood fabrication, leading to the current condition of 'information-tool-technology' [9]. This concept describes the use of automation to replace human labour, both physical and intellectual. In other words, from a time where a human operator exerted energy to operate a tool directly, to the era where machine energy supplanted this physical labour - i.e. machine-powered saws, drills - while still relying on the human for steering and control, the condition today is such where both energy and information processing are done by

FIG. The three areas and where they sit with respect to man and machine [9]

machines. These 'waves' are not meant to replace one-another, but are rather proposed as a layering of processes which the designer must understand in order to be effective and innovative. This has consequences both for the role of the designer-maker and the amount of information needed to produce artefacts. The designer-maker now has authority and control - therefore also responsibility - over the whole making process, and therefore the information demands and descriptions of the artefact become more and more complex.

What comes across from all of these approaches is that, yes, the introduction of computation and a materially-driven paradigm needs a thoughtful synthesis of all of those things involved - often posed in its ideal, most optimistic form as a seamless integration between all the different stages, scales, and stake-holders. While this can be demonstrated within controlled environments and selective case-studies, this smooth blending between parts is much more difficult to achieve in larger and more technically diverse environments. Indeed, oftenthe allure of architecture is its elegant assemblage of seemingly disjointed parts.

This is where a conflict arises: on the one hand, absolute integration - the soft blurring of hard domains and crystal-clear transparency through the whole depth of the process - requires all the participants be put under one common roof or else subjects them to some overarching system of authority. On the other hand, encapsulation - the precise delineation of boundaries, the autonomy of parts - simplifies the overall system but creates barriers for communication and knowledge transfer.

INTEGRATED PRACTICE

To address this dilemma, four examples from various types of practice are presented, each attempting to either side-step, anticipate, or mediate the chasm between ideal framework/integration and practical reality/implementation.

These frameworks are most readily implemented in research environments, indeed it is where they emerge: experimental research practices have the luxury of coming up with and testing new strategies that may not be readily applicable to the industry and market. It is no surprise, then, to see the most radical collaborations between design, research, and fabrication happen in this context, albeit at a smaller, more tentative scale (figure 3). These research-design-build practices benefit from a lower logistical overhead, more relaxed time-lines, and more speculative freedom compared to commercial practices that build buildings. While engaging with partners in industry - such as in the 55/02 shelter project by sixteenmakers* [10], where the design was negotiated within a tight collaboration between the researchers in the UK and a large-scale steel fabricator in Germany - these practices tend to build themselves around their research methods and individual projects. What this means is that the lifespan of the practice itself might only encompass a single project, therefore it avoids a large measure of risk which more permanent practices would have to take on. At best, this type of practice extends into a series of projects - for example, the suite of pavilions borne from a fruitful and ambitious collaboration between ICD and ITKE in Stuttgart [3] - building off of previous work and describing a broader research trajectory, with some of it hopefully finding its way into larger projects and industrial or market applications. The resultant work is informed wholly by the research questions and their relation to its

FIG. Research pavilion 2010 by ICD/itke, and 55/02 shelter by Sixteen makers

FIG. Shigeru Ban's Centre Pompidou-Metz

fabrication and material performance, unencumbered by questions of programme, function, or usage.

At the other end of the spectrum, the design, construction, and management of massive, geometrically complex timber buildings present a whole other set of issues. Apart from the sheer scale of operation, there now needs to be an extremely tight synchronization and negotiation between myriad other parties to ensure even a remotely successful outcome. The consequences are obvious: a small delay or mistake in one part of the complex design-development-production network could delay or even derail the whole project. This harrowing journey is exemplified in the description of the rationalization and logistical management of Shigeru Ban's Centre Pompidou-Metz (figure 4)[8]. The relationship between client, consultant, engineer, and fabricator illustrates how, even under the banner of the same project, different workflows and disparate conceptions of the project need to be interfaced and negotiated. Data needs to be exchanged, converted, re-modelled, and interpreted in as many steps as there are processes and domains of expertise (figure 5). It is this fragmentation

FIG. Software data flow between planning and fabrication in Shigeru Ban's Centre Pompidou-Metz

- largely unavoidable - of the different involved domains that makes it difficult to synthesize the pieces - in fact, it is exactly here where some form of integration would be most useful.

Design to production - the firm responsible for liaising with the timber fabricator, rationalizing the design models of the complex roof structure, and managing the creation and flow of fabrication data to the fabricator in the Pompidou-Metz project - proposes two possible areas of relief: the introduction of fabricators and associated consultants at a much earlier design phase - everyone sitting at the same table - and the development of fabrication information standards - a new data language for describing fabrication models in as generic terms as possible so that they can be propagated more easily throughout the whole design network [12]. While these may help to alleviate some of the complexity and risk involved, the success of the project still relies on multiple relatively disjunct domains of information.

These parcelled domains is exactly the kind of condition that Dsearch - the computational research unit within White Arkitekter, which in turn is a large, Scandinavian, multi-disciplinary architecture practice - confronts regularly. Dsearch investigates how computation can be deployed and integrated into large-scale architectural practice, and its position as a semi-autonomous research unit within White gives it a uniquely appropriate testing ground for this investigation. As a horizontally-organized practice, White lacks the top-down imperative structure in which decisions are passed down in a directed sequence of layers. This puts Dsearch in an interesting position of navigating between various design teams and other research units in a kind of organizational ecology, where different actors have very different needs, expectations, and skill sets. This profoundly affects the way in which the unit works, because all of these differing factors and roles need to be addressed and designed for. As a way of confronting this condition, the unit seeks to promote organizational learning across the firm through the overlaying of computational techniques onto

existing projects [6]. Instead of simply enforcing digital work standards and acting as a back-of-house tooling department, Dsearch looks at how information can be shared and communicated effectively throughout the practice, and how the project's design model can instead become a design system tailored to the project within such a collaborative environment. Central to their argument is the notion of Susan Leigh Star's 'boundary objects', objects or artefacts - real or virtual - which take on a different interpretation for different readers but ultimately provide a shared reference point for all involved[11]. These are posed as architectural models, representations, diagrams, scripts, and other notational objects that straddle the boundary between the separate groups at work, allowing them to collectively understand each other. This is reminiscent of Latour's imbroglios, entities which step horizontally across boundaries of domains and definitions, defying strict classification. Indeed, Dsearch and the integration of computational tools within any practice in general could be seen as such an elusive chimera: pervading the organizational structure of a practice, not quite here nor there, simulations that also send emails, live repositories for digital geometry as well as work schedules, where the seemingly simple act of drawing has consequences far beyond the printed page. This allows the interfacing of designers, consultants, researchers, and contractors, however barriers that could still prevent this from becoming a synthesized, integrated model across the whole breadth of the architectural project may have more political origins. For example, rules for tendering a project can prevent the architect from working directly with a contractor or fabricator at the early stage of a design until a contract bidding process has taken

FIG. The Dsearch service matrix, describing the role of Dsearch within partnerships and collaborations

place. This places the project out of the hands of the architect and at the whim of the specific capabilities and financial considerations of the chosen contractor when it comes to construction planning. No matter how well integrated and completely detailed, a timber project may end up being built out of poured concrete.

Finally, there is another material-based method of practice that exists somewhere between the first two examples. The previous example introduces the risk and larger institutional and political actors that come into play around the procurement of a project, which means that the architect must take on much more responsibility to be able to better control the output. Taking on more risk poses obvious challenges to a small- to mid-sized practice - the immanent threat of bankruptcy, for one - but it also allows a similar kind of material innovation that happens in research practice to make its way into commercial practice. To name but a single practice that works like this, Helen and Hard Architects - a Norwegian architecture firm that is pushing the field of timber construction in commercial and institutional projects - has a working model that demonstrates this possibility. For projects where they seek to use timber products in

FIG. Vennesla Library by Helen and Hard Architects

new ways, the practice takes on the research and production of full-scale prototypes and demonstrators, often not even involving the client until a working solution is ready. This means that a materially-driven method can be fleshed out and optimized before handing it off to a contractor, and the physical prototypes then become like a master carving of old or a template: to be copied and replicated instead of reinvented all over again through yet another process. The result is three things. As a tool of communication and even pedagogy, the full-scale demonstrator becomes the most direct way of communicating design intent and fabrication parameters to the builder. This potentially lowers the skill-level required to produce the parts, as it doesn't rely on the transfer and interpretation of complex data sets. Second, and following that, it has the advantage of lowering the risk for the contractor: there is much less ambiguity and unknown factors in the initial bid; the scope and requirements can be clearly seen. Finally, this allows the architect to pursue lines of research and real innovation in materials and fabrication techniques. The cost, of course, is a much higher degree of risk for the architect, instead of the contractor.

MAKING MODELS

So far several frameworks for material and fabrication integration into timber design have been presented, as well as some modes of practice which deal with the realities of such implementations. But what is central to all of those - and what they have been dancing around until now - is the actual object and its representation. How are these combinations of processes, strategies, collaborators - and so on - distilled down to some working model that is useful and related to the final, physical artefact? In other words, the duality of 'making models' - both 'how models are made' and 'models of the process of making' - becomes central to the discussion. It is at once a matter of communication - one of those imbroglios, perhaps - as well as an unambiguous, technical, parametric description of something that has very clear properties and dimensions. Two models that lie on either side are, therefore, useful to look at: the idea

of the morphospace, which represents the object as a whole multi-dimensional field of possibilities that is constrained by any number of design or fabrication parameters; and an example from the material sciences which examines four 'views' of a physical artefact, representing the main processes involved in its conception and the relationships between these processes.

The term 'morphospace' in architectural research is a borrowed term from theoretical morphology in biology to describe the space of possibilities that is defined by both design and fabrication parameters and their limits [4]. This spatializes the multitude of parameters and expresses their limits as multi-dimensional surfaces and boundaries (figure 8), where each parameter becomes a dimension. Any point on the inside of these volumes is within all the limits of the model, and vice versa for any point exterior to them. What this allows is a useful spatial correlation of parameters and the deployment of spatial search methods to find optimal design solutions. The solutions in this case are the physical artefacts, and the model parameters can be anything from fabrication parameters - tool length limits, machine axis limits, robot reach limits, etc. - to design drivers - area, angle constraints,

FIG. LEFT The morphospaces of a particular design problem [4]

FIG. RIGHT Four views of the real manufactured artefact [5]

available size of material, maximum curvature, etc. To arrive at a successful artefact, a suitable morphospace needs to be constructed that maps all the crucial limiting parameters onto a space, and then a point inside the resultant volumes simply needs to be picked. The design shifts towards the filtering and selection of parameters to include, and the relative importance of design factors - perhaps 'soft' areas within the morphospace. Also, while very suitable for parameters that are inherently dimensional - scalar values such as distances and angles - it is much more difficult to involve qualitative or other more 'fuzzy' properties within this model.

The second model comes from the material sciences and addresses the need for new models and representations of material behaviour and manufacturing processes which existing methods of surface and solid modelling cannot provide. Instead, it proposes that most computational tasks that affect the design and manufacture of an object can be framed by the relations between four 'views' surrounding the engineered artefact [5]. These views are all, in fact, different manifestations of the same object in different terms: the Functional view, the Designed view, the Planned view, the Simulated view, and, finally, the actual object - the Real view. This is a strongly manufacture-centric model and an effort to describe in greater detail a wider set of properties and qualities that revolve around the object. Although it is defined with a focus on additive manufacturing, an extension to this way of thinking could possibly find its way into timber prototyping in architecture as well. What is interesting is that it does not attempt to erase the multi-faceted nature of the artefact - surrounded as if by multiple atmospheres of different types and qualities of information - whereas the first model - the morphospace - seeks to unify the model's parts into a single common space, albeit a potentially unimaginably complex one. The two are probably not mutually exclusive: within the separate views of the engineered artefact, a morphospace could be developed to survey the object's potential configurations or to arrive at an optimized part of the design; or perhaps a morphospace could be created to specifically chart

spaces of overlap between views, or volumes of incompatibility. In any case, what this comparison illustrates is, as before, the potentially nebulous nature of computationally produced objects, once material behaviours and fabrication parameters begin to have an active and - at times - commanding voice in the design process.

THE PROJECT

This finally brings the discussion back to the project at hand. The project is positioned within this context of the frameworks, practices, and models outlined above and, to put it very broadly, asks what all of this means for engineered timber laminates. It seeks to address the discontinuity between those novel frameworks and the industrial-scale production of large architectural artefacts. Specifically, using the existing infrastructure of the contemporary engineered timber industry, the project asks how can novel methodologies which invoke and are driven by computation and material performance be deployed across a larger and more disparate design network.

The excited but often disruptive shift towards material-driven computational methodologies has stimulated much research and

FIG. A pointcloud representation of a glulam assembly

development around the behaviours and novel applications of wood. Its unique anisotropic properties, combined with glue-lamination and joinery techniques, present a set of ingredients with a rich potential for exploration. With these ideas in mind, there are two main thrusts of the project: to develop a material- and fabrication-based method and model of laminated timber - both as a morphospace of distinct parameters and as a layered panorama of the different 'views' that surround its process of becoming - and to connect this materially-driven way of designing to the practicalities of architectural practice and industrial production and their respective scales. The project is uniquely positioned to pursue these things, being partnered with both a multi-disciplinary architecture practice (White) and a leading timber fabricator (Timber Code).

The first aim needs to establish an appropriate model for glue-laminated timber, whether it is some combination of existing surface and mesh representations and simulation techniques, or a new type of representation for the fibrous and volumetrically-variant properties of large laminates, one that begins with the production life-cycle of existing timber products - from saw-mill to machining bed. Established industrial processes of making glulams and cross-laminated timber panels outline trajectories and boundaries of development. In order to contribute something novel, the project must be able to chart this territory and look for opportunities between these trajectories - perhaps hybridizing processes of fibre-directed glulams with other processes such as cross-lamination and block-gluing - and challenge the boundaries of what is currently possible.

The second aim needs to confront the communication and integration issues outlined in the practices above. Without attempting to solve the whole issue of communication in architecture, the project can offer a set of workflows and strategies that are specific to glue-laminated timber. This means interfacing the models from the first aim with design methods in practice and creating a framework that allows a comfortable collaboration between architect,

consultant, and fabricator. This also results in a densification or overlaying of the models with qualitative and non-scalar data, as it must recognize that certain computational design decisions carry with them consequences of risk, feasibility, and disruption in other involved domains.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

What - then - is the material practice of glue-laminated timber? What models can be deployed to address its behaviours and idiosyncrasies? How can the wealth of existing knowledge and practices around timber be used to establish a research methodology that is specific to timber and responsive to the industry's parameters and needs? How can fabrication-specific concerns be exposed and mediated in the early-stage design of timber assemblies?

The project seeks to address and answer these core questions through the experimentation, design and testing of material prototypes and information models that will filter and convey key data to multi-disciplinary design environments. It is through this effort that the project can begin to apply these new material-based frameworks to timber practice in a meaningful, relevant way.

FIG. Prototyping curved glulam beams

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Academic writing paper

Production with a purpose of study

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TRANSFERABLE SKILL COURSES

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the problem of architectural design imposed by the logic of computer optimization. The notion of 'optimal' is then situated in relation to, one might say, the parental notion of 'rational'. In order to define the difference between the two design driving ideas (that will later be read as modern and contemporary architectural order respectively), and to outline their contribution to the development of architectural form, a rather early example of modern design thinking would be involved in the investigated. Finally it is suggested that the essence of the contemporary order emanates from a particular mathematical method of structural optimization.

This logic is often referred to as a brute or even 'dumb', in this work is conceived as a dynamic actor that for the past two decades has shown an active ingression into design logic, from rather a superficial 'decorative' presence in the beginning to the current very seminal shift in understanding of the nature of space. This effect that in the end of XIX century was known as 'prehension', has recently been reinvented in the computational paradigm as 'contaminating', meaning that logic of computer algorithm is 'contagious' to designer's model of thinking, that it imposing new, perhaps post-human order in architecture.

I. 'Will to order' In the book "Architectures of Time: Toward a Theory of the Event in Modernist Culture" Sanford Kwinter speculates about form and novelty, space and time in relation to problem of change in architectural design practice. He writes: "...'possible' finds itself invariably placed in opposition to 'real' as if it were some type of earlier stage; it has on its own, therefore, no reality in the strict sense, but takes this on only at a later stage, through the process of realizing itself"[1]. I find this remark highly relevant to the discourse of computational design because every designer involved in it seeks, in one way or another, for a mean to sift the digital desert of possible in order to wash out grains of novelty, a new real. Whether it will be achieved purely through 'tacit' (if such a notion applies to the realm of computation) experience of the author or by employing mathematical functions depends on personal preferences. However this two pathways lead to results distinctive in form, which I believe derive from designer's relation to the tool he or she uses. Computer in a role of design tool conventionally understood as a medium for modelling and representation. However such a reading inevitably reduces the field of computationally possible designs, simply turning the format of drawing from analogue to digital. It might be helpful now to introduce the notion of metamodeling, coined by Felix Guattari [2], and situated in architectural discourse by Luciana Parisi, who suggests that in relation to computation, metamodeling "describes... how potentialities exceed preordained typologies" [3]. Such a concept, without a doubt, responds to the highest expectations from the use of computer, namely generative forces of speculative computation. However it does bring architects to overwhelmingly reach field of possibilities, quite often resulting in long term frustration. Sanford Kwinter provides a definition of architecture that might help to resolve this situation: "Architecture's proper and primary function, it could be said – at least in the modern era – is the instrumental application of mastery, not only to an external, non-human nature, but to a human – social, psychological – nature as well. This method in no way excludes a guerilla architecture of subversion and resistance, such as the active "resingularizing" of the familiar and precoded, amplifying

the transformative power of the contingent through an ethics of flexible, or “opportunistic” vigilance, or tapping the history reducing forces of the emergent and untimely.” [5] Apart of the fact that the notion of ‘mastery’ appears here due to the preceding reference to ideas of M. Foucault [6], the comprehension of this sentence is useful and may further be applied when describing the unstable position of architects rebelling against externally imposed tool. As a tool I tend to consider design software. Architects do rebel in a productive way, adjusting and customizing programs, but not necessarily because they want to develop software products. What seems to be the problem here is a software, a design operative system (it would in fact sometimes even be called ‘architecture’) imposing artificial, arbitrary order to the user. I would like to claim that this type of underlying order of things formerly has been only under architect’s command, depicted in pale pencil lines of a drawing. But in no way architects rebel because they don’t trust software developers, rather it is due to the great potential of computer, and particularly saying CAD discretized environment. It can even be called actualized space, since it supports radically new design strategies and thinking, and allows to document conditions of form and function that architect by no means could have mediated a century ago. With the slowly coming comprehension of how computation might be useful for architectural design, and first of all design of form, the understanding of ‘instrumental application of mastery’ gets unavoidably related to programing.

II. Logical: Rational, Optimal In light of above mention I would like to reformulate a problem that has been already at stake at least since 90s, since it was brought into discussion in works of Bonnie A. Nardi. In the book called “A Small Matter of Programming” [7] he has defined two different ways of using software, therefore dividing in two categories computer users in accordance to their relation to software. The first is the group that was heard to remark: “I didn’t have much time, so I did it the long way”; the second group states the converse: “I would rather write programs to help me write programs

than write programs". I would then argue that the gradient field set by these extremes has withstood all the permutations of the past decades, remained till today, and most likely will not ever leave the digital paradigm. However out of the list of professions which Nardi has qualified as 'not programmers', architects are probably the only who insistently don't want to submit. I tend to relate it with that designers, and especially architects, distrust software, and more generally operative system, designed and imposed from outside of architectural realm, like if it was some kind of a mediator that stood up between architect and his project. Architectural tradition requires architect to have the most direct, non-interrupted access to the hidden order of form, which adjustments will cause 'architectural' changes in form. This, in a way heuristic nature of architectural practice, defines the root of distrust in regards to the ready-made computational tools. This circumstance, I believe, explains the popularity of means of visual programming, propagated by Nardi already in early 90s, that liberates architect from the end-user status and therefore allows to modify the order of mathematical operations that facilitate a design relevant computation processes without excessive knowledge in programming languages. As Sanford Kwinter approaches the problem of architectural form and will to order he writes: "No genealogy of the body in relation to Western architectural mastery is possible, even today, that does not begin by reviving, at least in passage, the convention of Vitruvian man splayed out and mathematically embedded in a reticulum of regulating lines like a proud trophy honoring the Idea and geometric exactitude." This idea is followed by the statement that in Western paradigm "...the histories of the body itself, of architecture, and of the even more basic "will to order" are inseparable from one another."

[8] The problem of algorithmic ingression in architecture has its own history. As early as 1963 Christopher Alexander stated, that "Logic, like mathematics, is regarded by many designers with suspicion. Much of it is based on various superstitions about the kind of force logic has in telling us what to do." Furthermore, Alexander claims that "the word 'logic' has some currency among designers as a reference

to a particularly displeasing and functionally unprofitable kind of formalism" [9]. I tend to think that in exactly that time Alexander was talking about 'logic' of cybernetics, more as a dynamic process rather than a set of rules. Otherwise it will be hard to imagine that in 60s North American architects were still standing aloof, from, for instance, ideas of Adolf Loos and his 'reductionist' experiments conducted by simply qualifying architectural form in two types: what was arbitrary and seminal in architectural linguistics of form that only aims to transmit architect's expression of order. Assumingly, in this context logic is fighting with superstition and it was exactly designer's superstition that caused excessive destabilization and determination, characteristic not only to Vienna Secession but to all Art deco schools, that in Loos view were disturbing the order. Notice that Loos was arguing against redundancy of form while still implementing elements of Tuscan order in his most resonant project of Goldman & Salatsch Building in 1910. Tuscan order, a peculiar invention of Italian Renaissance, a 'reformed' version of the classical Doric order. Tuscan order disregards rudimentary flutes as well as Vitruvian narrative superstition – Tuscan columns combine manly Doric roughness of form with Ionic feminine pillow base. To a great extent Loos is a successor of this type of thinking. To emphasize the conceptual value of the Tuscan porch, four columns were produce out of single pieces of jewel-like marble. I'd like to emphasize that already by 60s such columns will make zero sense and nothing on earth will justify them as progressive. Indeed, looking from the rational point of view, Loos House is barely half way rational. It was industrial design that soon after imposes its manufacturing standards of mass products on architectural order of rationality. After the war, Western design logic that was revolutionary even a while ago have finally crystalized: became fixed and clear, intrinsic and inseparable from the discipline of design. "Form follows function" is just one of many reminiscences of definitions that polished the idea of modern logic in relation to design. In light of this, the problem that Alexander rose significantly descends from the following reactionary logic of postmodernity. Important however is that in postmodern times the

idea of computer has invited many to speculate of new ideas of order in architecture. Yet, except of very few basic concepts of cybernetics that were adopted but scarcely useful in regular architectural practice, the postmodern mechanism of logic was majorly based on seizing the extreme conditions of modern rationality, and from that point of view constructing critical arguments. Therefore I would argue that postmodern concepts served merely as a vehicle between the modern idea of rational, and what was anticipated with development of computation - the phenomenon of optimal. Currently optimal can be comprehended as the ultimate design quality which seems to be the essence of the most rigorous pragmatism imprinted in form. Its tendency to converge all options into the optimal one significantly differs it from the rational, which due to its democratic roots did not reduce design variations to only one. By the very nature of its totality its optimization can't be democratic; it awakes subconscious anxiety that in its turn triggers idea of distopia or notopia [10] which preconditions the increasing popularity of this terms. It is definitely hard to comprehend the reason why optimization that should have brought us to something positive or even optimistic results in the very opposite. For instance, in business management, especially in countries where protection of worker's rights is not the priority of the government, the term optimization is used to describe a severe mode of corporate human resources policy, that is often regarded as one aspect of a broad campaign of cutting down excessive expenses. Therefore optimization can be characterized as contraction. Symptomatically, improvements in the sphere of IT are often concomitant and allow to minimize human labor hours.

III. 'A comparative case study' In architecture, however, the attitude to optimization remains uncertain. It is due to the specifics of the discipline – not many actually share a concern in the influence imposed by the established software. Even such an obvious thing as the influence of CAD environment on the resulting design many will consider as arguable. Even conservationists are not necessarily convinced with a gloom consequences of optimization thinking:

even the most merciless critic of an environmental activist can be corrupted by optimization's reduced waste and energy consumption. They however underestimate one important aspect: the software that we use to optimize is not equivalent to a catalogue of standards, or trigonometric table. The means of optimization instead are active members of a design process; it is simply inapplicable without automation. From within the automation, I believe, derives the emergent concept of post-human order – the order accessible only through computation. I will therefore proceed with an example of a configuration such a mathematical and computation setup that already today allows to implement this order in computer-aided design practices. In order to stronger outline the direction in which the design logic is heading I would like now to compare two examples of chair design and extract the design logic in relation to its form. It will be a chair that is constantly leaving, constantly temporary but is always there in our life. It will be opposed to a design that is coming and on the basis of this design intention it is conceived as some extraordinary product.

The examples are: the world's most common plastic chair, truly the icon of rationality entitled Monobloc [11], and one out of many prototypes of a chair design with use of structural optimization algorithms and additive methods of fabrication [12]. I consider that both examples are highly symptomatic for their individual design paradigm, and the comparison will allow to see additional valuable aspects which are normally hidden. The word Monobloc rather stands for the concept of fabrication than for a particular design. Indeed it is an icon of rationality – a chair that is a classic design challenge, is resolved on an unprecedented level of resource economy. The fabrication requires half a kilo polypropylene and a reusable two-part mold; the process of forming takes scarcely a minute. It is light, enduring, stackable, weather resistant, etc. It is simply democratic good. Regarding its invention some sources claim that the idea of fabricating a chair in one single piece has first come in 1946 to a Canadian architect D.C. Simpson [10]. Somehow or other by 1960s the idea has already spread over ocean and a number of designers

were producing their variations all across Europe. However it was only in 1983 when a design developed by a Spanish corporation Grosfillex group dominated the market with a variation that has soon become the most ubiquitous street furniture object around the world. Due to the laws of the market economy the retail sales that started at the level of \$50 has burst as price reached its current fair \$10 per chair, still bringing approximately 300% of profit.

The story of the Monobloc is an outstanding case of how an idea or invention has been developed through consistent redesigning into a masterpiece of mass consumption. Let us notice, however, that before arriving to the chair that is now in every backyard, the idea has undergone extreme permutations. Just as an example, in 1971 Studio 65 has design a set of chairs called Capitello [13]. By exploiting the similar fabrication principals of injection molding, designers arrived to a whole set of furniture that plays with cartoonish representation of elements of Greek orders. The postmodern irony can be found on different levels, for instance designer has reflected on the concept of "stackable" chair – columns, bases and capitals made of foam and adjusted to sitting or other ordinary functions can be assembled into a column. Yet it was only a ridiculous eccentricity of design permutations which apparently has contributed to the form of the Monobloc of 1983, which previously flat and solid surfaces has now become 'fluted'. Let's now switch the chair to the one design in 2014. It is called Generico and it has been exhibited on Milan Design Week in the same year. Like a proper piece of architecture the chair is a result of collaboration between architects Marco Hemmerling and Ulrich Nether, and engineer Mathias Michel. But to be honest, Generico is not properly a chair. Hemmerling describes it as follows: "Generico is a prototype for a new way of design thinking, developed with a holistic approach using latest technologies. The design is based on the requirements of comfortable sitting and responds to load forces and ergonomic conditions." [14] Indeed it is a sample of design methodology encompassing a set of the most recent technologies from advanced structural analysis to additive fabrication, where

the whole process of design is inseparable from computation and seems not to be feasible without it. In a review by the online issue Designboom it was stated that “a material layout calculation resulted in reducing parts of the volume”, assumingly removing material from where it is not needed and adding it where the stress is. This is a basic definition of structural (or topological) optimization – an algorithmic generative process that, by utilizing mathematical system of finite element method, solves structural problems with minimum amount of material. Paradoxically, the optimized geometry is completely the opposite of what was considered to be rational in the modern sense. The accompanying technology of 3D printing of course eases the transition from digital model to the material prototype, but so far it does not solve the problem of mass fabrication. This is the first, rather superficial difference from the Monobloc. However there is no point in the critique based on the aspects authors consciously decided to disregard, so I will move on to the second distinction.

The second distinction that I will further focus on I believe is more prolific for speculations. In contrast with the Monobloc (where a new material – plastic, and its related technologies of forming have stimulated the evolution of design logic), the impetus today, it can be said, emanates from the opposite end of the design-to-fabrication workflow. Optimized design propagates a new idea of order. Precisely speaking it comes from the discretized space of CAD modelling environment that allows new ways of managing and documenting complexity of form. Such an environment allows not only to construct a model of design in no time and at no expenses but, if advanced with means of visual programming it provides a ground for implementation of radically novel methods. The one that has been implemented in the Generico chair is the one that governs form as no other – it is structural optimization algorithm that incorporates the FEM.

Erick Winsberg, philosopher of science, who is not in a direct way related to architectural discourse, writes that: “Finite differencing is a

discretization of both space and time. But discretization can occur in time but not in space: in this latter case, one uses a set of (complete in some norm) basis functions to transform the spatial part of the equations, so that the partial differential equation is turned into a set of (coupled) ordinary differential equations for the coefficients of the basis functions." [15] Further he remarks that simplification of an equation by discretization inevitably leads to 'averaging' the problem. Apparently there is no alternative of increasing accuracy than simply increasing the resolution of discrete units, therefore again "solving them by brute force". Nevertheless in the conditions of constantly increasing processing power, this seems question of resolution seem to be just a matter of time. However the mathematical concept of finite element analysis, or even more accurately finite difference method, provides Roughly speaking it is achieved in two steps: solution for engineering problems in a new way. **A.** 'Voxelization'¹⁶ of space region that includes the constructive problem; **B.** Composing and computing differential equation for each voxel in relation to the rest. Even though FEM principals were invented before cybernetics, still without computation it was not rational to use methods requiring such massive calculations to solve constructive problems as trivial as a chair. In fact, the method of finite elements resembles hacking - reinforced with computation it runs as long as it takes to solve a constructed equation. Arguably this way of solving design problems has no precedence in history, it is therefore the one that constitutes the emergent order of computational governance over form. Yet it stays merely as a simulation of the order since we don't possess sufficient means for the form of such a complexity to be embodied in material of architectural scale. It is truly the order of massive digital simulation since the very process of morphogenesis that happens in this voxelized space shows a total indifference about how this complexity will be constructed.

CONCLUSION

Concluding, I would like to situate the term of simulation. Nowadays it covers a broad and very diverse field of computation. One

can easily meet its application all along the frontier of science: from astrophysics where it is used to prove hypothesis, through all possible applications in physics, engineering, chemistry and industry to biology and development of artificial intelligence. Oxford dictionary defines it as 'the production of a computer model of something, especially for the purpose of study'. That is, digital simulation is used as a regular epistemological tool, merely a mean to conduct mathematical experiments. For sure it is a challenge because a problem that biologist faces in biology needs to be first represented as a system of equations, which sometimes is far from being easy. In this sense it is alike with modelling some phenomenon in mathematic definition. Rather simplified, simulation of this case merely allows to compare a mathematical model with an observed phenomenon in nature. Even though architecture is closely bound to computational techniques of modelling, still architects who dive in the realm of programming try to use it as an exploratory, rather generative tool. There is a risk, however, that architectural design practice as an activity very vulnerable to the cultural environment can start mimicking the finite element logic. Mario Carpo articulates the problem by explicitly saying that designers can now use "...data-driven, 'dumb' approach to test complex quantitative phenomena ... without the need to interpret them through cause-and-effect, deterministic rules or models" [16]. The problem, which in Alfred North Whitehead's terms sounds as 'prehension', and that recourse in writings of Sanford Kwinter, and later is placed in computational context by Luciana Parisi as 'contagion', suggests that the nature of the new order governed by the new mathematical structure of simulation is slowly spreading the encrypting the nature further along the stream of the design-to-fabrication flow. The actualization that will then happen will definitely be a sonorous one.

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Academic writing paper

Modeling Architectural Problems for Artificial Intelligence in order to Support Human Machine Interaction in Early Design Phase

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ABSTRACT

The integration of machine intelligence into creative process can open up new possibilities to investigate solution space. Here the computer becomes a stakeholder in the decision making process. Accordingly, the creative process of design turns into an interaction between two different kind of intelligences belonging to different kinds of species. In order to involve the computer correctly within the process a common ground of communication should be developed. Here the modeling of the problem becomes essential. The article investigates the existing involvement of machine intelligence into the early design phase and proposes a problem modeling method that is used to train a machine learning algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

In his article "Towards Humanism Through Machines" Nicolas Negroponte outlines the distinction between computerized and computer-aided processes.

For Negroponte the computerized processes are programs that are used for calculate certain outputs in user's command building a master (designer) slave (the computer) relation between both parties.

On the other hand, computer-aided processes are framed as the interaction of two different kind of intelligences with the equal influence of both parties in the decision making process. [1]

The immense complexity of the design problems requires extra stakeholders with different qualities participating in the design process. Involving different points of view, integrating different disciplines in order to find an ideal solution for a design problem. Such interdisciplinary collaboration is integrated deeply in the architectural and engineering practices today. The machine intelligence with its ability to recognize patterns that the human stakeholders may not be aware of, is of a high importance for a more integrated and creative design thinking. The lacking human intuition in the machine intelligence carries the process of design into a new association between two species which continuously influence each other during the search for an idealized design solution.

In his musicolour machine Gordon Pask observes the creative process emerging through human machine collaboration. The musicolour machine is a system that trains an intelligent machine by the musician's interaction with the machine, in this case by playing the piano. The machine analyses the patterns in the composition and reacts to these by outputting colored lights. The recurrent interaction created by such a feedback loop pushes the composer to change the composition reacting the outputs of machine and vice versa machine continuously changes the output by reacting to the changes in the composition. In this way machine becomes an extension of the human creativity, by introducing a different kind of intelligence in this process. [2]

In order to involve the computer as an extra stakeholder in the creative process the communication between the user and the machine is an essential part. The communication of these two different intelligences can only occur through the correct formulation of the certain

problem in a common language. This language can be developed by understanding the behavioral patterns of the different machine learning methods and their capabilities in the certain problem setting and as well as looking into the problem description methods in other disciplines than design, which are commonly using machine learning strategies. A deep understanding of the system modeling approaches existing in the different scientific fields can be an important step to inform the design discipline in formulating the problems correctly, in order to construct an associative relationship between the designer and the machine.

This article discusses the benefits of integrating machine intelligence into the creative processes by concentrating on the communication between human and machine. The focus is set on finding a common ground for the communication between these two stakeholders, therefore the article concentrates on the systems modeling and provides an overview on a problem description method that can be used for training a backpropagation algorithm to be able to participate in decision making process in development of complex urban morphologies.

MODELING SYSTEMS

As Ludwig von Bertalanffy points out different fields of science share structural similarities or what is also called isomorphisms in the principles that govern the behavior of the entities, that are intrinsically and widely different. He argues that, each system either it is physical or chemical or biological is a kind of abstraction that is created by the human mind and explained by the mathematical equations. These mathematical equations though are correspondent in different fields of science and therefore many phenomena regardless the scientific discipline can be explained with a similar systems approach. [3]

However, the systems modeling approaches require a high abstraction of the complex systems in order to match this for a certain modeling

approach. The abstraction of the system is also called idealization in modelling in philosophy of science. [4] The idealization in this context is an intended oversimplification in the representation of the target system. One of the commonly used methods in the sciences is the specific modeling approach, where the system is reduced to a specific set of features which are called abstract universals. The abstract universals are referring to the features of one idealized generic object. These idealized object is defined by the user relying on an idealized expected outcome of the problem. In order to define a particular object, the deviation of object's features from the abstract universals are calculated. [5]

This method can be compared to the commonly used stochastic processes in architecture and engineering as a tool of optimization. Looking into the processes such as gradient descent based optimization or genetic algorithms, a design model is reduced into a parametric model (mathematical equation) which is divided into parameters and objectives, where the parameters are being the variables in the equation and the objectives being the intended results in this case can also be called abstract universals.

Both of the previously mentioned optimization methods are used for searching for an optimal solution by trying to minimize the objective function. In this case the design solutions quickly converge into particular ideal solutions proposed by the computer. The computer is limited to the search space that the user has generated within the domains of the predefined variables, and the output is an intense calculation basing of combinations of the variables in an iterative process. Here rather than influencing the user's decision the computer is used again as a tool to conduct immense calculations in a short period of time.

These systems approach combined with the optimization can be very effective in the later phases of design development where a certain design problem is outlined and the stochastic search becomes essential in order to optimize the conflicting criteria. However, in

early design phases although there are several design constraints the design objectives are continuously shifting. One can say that the early design phase is a search for the objectives and parameters within the given constraints of the design brief. In a better explanation the early design phase is a search for model description. In this case since the lack of steady objective values prevent the abstract universals to be predefined correctly. Therefore, in order to define the specific objects (or evaluate solutions) another type of modelling should be used.

In the earlier phases of design investigating the solutions according to the similarities in between and their topological relations within each other might be more beneficial rather than evaluating the solutions according to explicitly set objectives that might not even be correctly defined on the first hand. Therefore, in these phases a self-referential modeling approach might be a better solution, where the search for a good solution is conducted by visiting the benefits and limitations of different possibilities.

Looking into the machine learning strategies the ability of these methods to classify the objects (solutions) within the given data set rather than referring to external objective values makes these methods very attractive for the early phases of design. The self-referential data models generate an idealized model building upon the comparison of the objects in the given data set. The changes in the data set also changes the idealized model. Each object in the data set is described by their own features and their deviations from the other objects and idealized model. Basically, these processes can be scaled by scaling the data set. The adjustability of the machine learning processes to the size of the data set seems very promising for the early design phases.

BREAKING DOWN THE PROBLEM

The extreme flexibility of artificial neural networks (ANN) can be observed in the applications of these in different fields of science. The flexibility of the system setup provides them with the ability to form complex relationships between input and output streams. As a consequence of this neural networks are able to discover patterns within the data set which might be impossible to recognize for human intelligence. In the application of these methods in the design processes, the ANNs can discover recurrent patterns in the creative process which might be impossible for the human intuition to be aware of. Through the involvement of this kind of an analytic intelligence in the design process the recurrent interaction between the designer and the machine can be activated, where machine is involved as another decision maker by providing the designer with suggestions basing on the analytical observation of designer's decisions.

In this collaborative approach the correct introduction of the design problem to the machine becomes essential. This introduction should be similar to a linguistic evolution. Each should track the others' maneuvers evoking a rhetoric that cannot be anticipated. The event is circular since the designer – machine unity provokes a dialogue and the dialogue provokes a stronger unity. [6]

The methods to describe the problem to the machine are similar in different fields of application. Initially the solution is divided into smaller bits and the analysis of these smaller bits are analyzed in order to draw general conclusions. In case of image recognition and classification the image is divided into a number of equal sized pixels. The color information (as RGB values or similar) in these pixels construct the input 'neurons' for the machine learning algorithm. Each solution is classified according to similarities of the color values in relation to the coordinates of the pixels in the image (in this case the neurons that they rely on). The images that share the similar color information in the same or similar coordinates are considered

to be related or similar to each other. The more pixels share similar information the closer is the relation between the images. The architectural application of such a system can be very beneficial in handling complex models such as urban or structural systems. In the case of the article, the authors define the shape features by a localized description of a sample point or vertex, which constitutes the input vector for the machine learning. (Figure 1) [7] By using this methodology each model is broken down into smaller solutions, as a consequence a larger set of data constituted from the point information emerges from a smaller set of building models. This way the authors succeed to create a large training set out of 600 building instances.

FIG. Wilkinson, S., Hanna, S. (2014). International Journal of Architectural Computing, 12(2), pp.155-178

CASE STUDIES

This chapter represents a problem description method developed relying on the method in the previously mentioned article by Sean Hanna and Samuel Wilkinson. The problem studies the potentials of training an ANN on a smaller urban patch in order to develop generic rules for a larger urban system. The aim of the experiment is to investigate the possibilities of parameter extrapolation with the ANN rather than deriving performance data by approximating objective function. In large design problems such as urban design, the system complexity becomes very high very quickly. Therefore, in these projects the iterative search algorithms such as genetic algorithms become cumbersome and ineffective. This experiment tackles with these problems and tries to develop a new system model to investigate the search space.

The initial idea for this experiment originate from problems experienced during the design process of another urban project at the Architectural Association in Emergent Technologies and Design Studio. (Figure 2) In this urban experiment the emergent design processes were investigated by breaking down an urban setting into a system of interacting rules. In the developed methods the problem was broken down into two major steps where in each step a genetic algorithm (in this case the Experiments were conducted using Octopus plug in for Grasshopper in Rhino) was used in the decision making process, in order to discover solutions regarding conflicting goals preset by the designers. In this setup the first step was the two-dimensional generation of a masterplan on a 2 km² urban area. Building upon the information extracted from the first step an urban morphology was generated with newly set objectives that influence the design in the third dimension. Even though in the first step the use of a genetic algorithm was very effective to search the solution space in order to find a satisfying outcome, during the second step difficulties were experienced in the use of the genetic algorithm. The issue here was the iterative way that the GA works was not really efficient for the increased complexity of the urban system which was

requiring creation and analysis of larger solution sets in the second step. Increasing the geometric complexity in a large area increased the computation time drastically and this ended up in not being able to generate and evaluate many solutions in a feasible time period, which also ended up in an ineffective use of a GA almost outside of its domain. The experiment ended up generating the morphologies manually without evaluating these regarding any objective.

Moving on from afore mentioned experiment, a new model was generated in order to train the ANN. This experiment only aims to test the feasibility of the system therefore no particular urban setting was selected. The experiment was conducted in an imaginary urban setting. Also the number of parameters and objectives were limited to 5 parameters and 3 objectives in order to test the method on a simple setting to avoid large computation periods. This experiment was conducted in Grasshopper environment using the extension tools of Octopus-e Plug-in created by Robert Vierlinger. The experiments start with redefining an urban problem in a smaller area, regarding possibilities that can be encountered in an urban setting. The ANN

FIG. Kabarra, A., Zaldivar, D., Kravchenko, O., Aksoz, Z. Core studio II. Emergent Technologies and Design Program Architectural Association, 2014

will be trained in this smaller patch and the rules extracted from this patch will be applied to a larger urban setting. This way experiment aims to skip the optimization simulation in the larger urban area by using a GA and extrapolate the information from the training data on a smaller patch. The experiment sequence is as described below (Figure 3):

- Train an ANN on a small patch that inherits different urban situations
- Validate this ANN on the small patch by using the training set as the

validation set

- Apply the trained ANN on an explicitly generated urban masterplan
- A combination of conflicting goals was selected regarding environmental performance and density of the urban setting. In this setup the objectives were set to increase the environmental performance by minimizing the ground shadow and maximizing the surface exposure and limiting the floor area ratio (FAR) to a maximum of 11 which encountered in the high dense financial district of London. All three objectives set up a conflicting system. The minimization of ground shadow requires smaller buildings for the optimization, however increase of the FAR and the ground exposure require taller building morphologies. The first two objectives depend on the neighborhood relation of each plot and the morphology of the building, such as building orientation to the selected sun vectors and building height whereas the third one is only related to the building morphology such as plot coverage and building height.

Since the two environmental objectives were highly related to the neighborhood relation of each particular cell, the size of the training patch was selected according to the variety of the neighborhood relations that can be obtained within an urban setting. These are edge situations with five neighboring cells, corner situations with three neighboring cells, and center situations with eight neighboring cells. These situations should be inherited within the training patch in order to be able to calculate different shadow and surface exposure situations that depend on the neighbors. Therefore, the training

examples were generated basing on a patch of $3 \times 3 = 9$ cells. For the training 67 different types of a 3×3 grid was generated and depending on this grid each cell was populated with a different morphology. In the generation of training examples 5 parameters were used, where the first three were used to generate the grid cells by setting up the plot width, plot depth and street offset, and the last two were set up for the generation of the building morphology in each grid cell. In this case these parameters were the coverage and morphology of the footprint on the plot and the building height. The ground shadow, surface exposure and FAR was calculated for each cell in regard to its neighbors. these values were recorded along with the parameter values for each particular cell (Figure 4).

Considering the main interest of using the ANN as a stakeholder that participates in the decision making; in the training process the input parameters were set to objective values – in this case the input will be the target values for objectives, defined by the user – neighborhood relation of each cell in 0s and 1s (0 being no neighbor in the certain

FIG. Parameters and Objectives

grid coordinate and 1 is being having a neighbor at the certain grid coordinate) and as the last, the parameters of the grid such as grid size and the street offset which will be given in the explicitly generated masterplan. It was expected that the ANN can suggest morphologic parameters relying on the provided inputs, in consequence output parameters were selected as the parameters that relate to plot coverage, plot morphology and building height (Figure 5). This setting provided the ANN with $67 \times 9 = 603$ different solutions, since each small patch was also broken down into single solutions -in this case buildings- to train the network. Similar to the method in [10] the time consuming generation and analysis of a larger training set was avoided by using a meta sized patch that is broken down into smaller entities. (Figure 6). After the training the ANN was validated firstly with the same training set in order to understand whether the provided suggestions were displaying too much deviation from the actual parameters. In this case the ANN was displaying certain deviations which can be decreased by increasing the number of solutions in the

FIG. Inputs and outputs

training set. Secondly the trained neural network was applied on a previously generated urban masterplan composed by 2500 different sized cells with varying neighborhood relations in order to test the machine performance in the generation of the entire urban area. The calculation of the parameters less than a minute, where generating the entire model took around 90 minutes. (Figure 7)

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, NEXT STEPS

Describing a problem correctly is one of the essential points in the human-computer interaction. The correct communication between both parties can result in the most beneficial collaboration. In order to find the right description methodology, the behavior of the machine learning algorithms should be well investigated. The wide application of the machine learning strategies can provide an array of problem description methods integrated and experimented in other disciplines. Since this is an ongoing experiment the conclusions are only derived from the sub-steps. There are certain limitations in the method that is selected for the creation of the training set. Firstly, the recent training set consisting of 9 cells displays too many corner and edge situations in relation to the central situations. However, in a larger urban setting the mostly encountered situations are buildings that are central or neighboring 8 cells, rather than the corners and edges. Since the ANNs tend to extract the patterns regarding to mostly encountered training examples this trained network might draw generalizations according to these mostly occurring situations. Therefore, the size of the training patch has to be adjusted to overcome these issues.

FIG. Randomly generated training set

This case study is the start of an array of different experiments with a similar problem break down methodology. In the next steps it is aimed to involve structural problems and draw a comparison between these two different kinds of design settings.

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Academic Writing: Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS

Through review of the submitted papers (published in the previous pages) it is clear that students successfully developed papers covering their individual research topics and engaged in a productive peer-review process within the ESR group. From student feedback it is clear that the process of reviewing papers written by their peers added an additional positive learning outcome to the taught material. It is anticipated that further papers will be received during the second year and that the students will make use of the workshop in their publication of papers external to the network.

Furthermore, the course made use of the Podio collaboration platform as a vehicle for the sharing of written material and discussions that stemmed from this.

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Robotic Steering and Control

IAAC (BARCELONA)
04 - 08 JULY 2016

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SCIENTIFIC COURSES

Led by: Alexandre Dubor and Djordje Stanojevic

INTRODUCTION TO THE SEMINAR

Robotic steering and control introduced alternative robotic control protocols for design based interfaces.

Starting from basics of robotic kinematics, different strategies were explored for path planning with Rhino & Grasshopper through the integration of the robot 6+1 axis. The background was defined by the additive manufacturing and robotic fabrication knowledge developed extensively over the last couple of years at the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia. Tools for extrusion and various types of clay were provided by the Institute, as well as the digital and hands-on support during the development of the workshop. To enrich the content of the course, material performance through different composition and fabrication methodologies were proposed for the exploration and idealisation of new possibilities at the architectural scale. Therefore, having the goal to build on these precedents, the focus was set to be explicitly on the process. Specific additions to the course were the introduction to the Kuka Robotic Language (KRL), Arduino, and Processing towards the establishment of a real time feedback loop from the physical to the digital world. Based on that, the students were interactively exploring robotic extrusion with an Emerging design approach.

SUMMARY OF THE ALL THE PROJECTS DURING THE WORKSHOP

The participants were divided into four groups and invited to develop their own fabrication process, as well as rethinking the way we use the extrusion system. The teams focused on testing cantilevering limits, integration of an external axis, support of sensors, and inflatable formwork.

FIG. LEFT PAGE Geodesically-driven multi-axis clay deposition by A. Prior, T. Svilans and J. Solly

Group 1: Interactive Pottery Wheel

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The project's aim was to create an interactive pottery wheel, a robotically clay printing machine which can be controlled by hand gestures. The development of the project built upon the taught clay printing technique by adding new functionality to the process. At first, several experiments were made to assess the maximum deviation of the clay printing per layer, which concluded to be 30 degrees. At a next step the GH definition was further developed, using advanced KRL functions to allow for interactive control of the robot. The robot was connected to an arduino beared with an infrared sensor which was used to control the deviation from the starting path of the fabrication. The end result was a live demo of the interactive pottery wheel.

FIG. Interactive pottery wheel

Group 2: Geodesically-Driven Multi-Axis Clay Depositioning

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Geodesic clay extrusion with 6-axis robot and additional external rotating axis. The research explored a "surface tangent aligned tool orientation" along geodesic path. Therefore, the robot wrist rotation was constrained to only the altitude of the geometric normals while the external axis was orienting the mesh towards the robot wrist. Emerging considerations about the material performance were looking at the exploration of Constant Z-section distribution against Geodesic curve distribution across the input geometry. The machining environment was parallelly focusing on the toolpath in Cartesian space against the toolpath accommodating an external axis.

FIG. Geodesically-driven multi-axis clay deposition

Group 3: Cantilevering and collapsing through machine learning algorithms

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Cantilevering and collapsing were selected as the main optimisation goals while producing the 3d printed clay structures. By testing the extreme cantilever and letting structures collapse the limitations in the physical environment can be recorded and feedback into the computer model, where then regarding these limitations geometries that can be optimized for cantilevering can be produced by the computer. The computational process was basing on three different machine learning algorithms, and a Kohonen Map (of Self Organizing Map) was used in order to create many samples.

Fabrication Process

FIG. Cantilevering and collapsing through machine learning algorithms

Group 4: Weaving and pneumatic formwork

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The focus of the workshop consists of two main concepts; i.e. weaving and pneumatic formwork. The first one's interest was shown in the tectonic of the surface and notion of a robotic gesture. The analogue of sedimentation became replaced with that of the concept behind weaving. The other line of investigation involved the possibility of depositing material on top of an existing topography, i.e. generating an inner space. The prospect with such an exploration includes possibility of site specific interventions and make additions to existing structures. This enables the possibility of generating spatial structures that ignore gravitational forces during fabrication. For the purpose of the workshop a pneumatic formwork was chosen to utilize the advantage of this fabrication process, i.e. the ability to design a structure that becomes self-supporting when the clay has dried and the formwork is deflated and removed.

Freedom and possibility to interactively adapt the geometry during the fabrication according to the rules he has set before.

FIG. Weaving and pneumatic formwork

Robotic Steering and Control: Reflections

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SCIENTIFIC COURSES

REFLECTION ON THE SEMINAR

This type of course make us grow as researchers and increase our knowledge in different areas. From start the participants demonstrated high competence in computation and fabrication. By merging their background in groups, the outcomes were pleasantly unexpected. Using the physical feedback from the printing process in order to optimize the geometry, exploring material and geometric limits and creating real-time feedback loops, the students materialised inspiring outcomes. The approach to the course archived several clay prototypes and demonstrated how new fabrication strategies can emerge by exploring the process instead of starting from a form. In this study case the sensor interface implementation brought to evidence that the real time technology can be compared with sculpting more than with a linear process, where the robot does not depend on a determinate control code but works as a direct tool for materialisation. Here, the user has the freedom and possibility to interactively adapt the geometry during the fabrication according to the rules he has set before.

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